

The interaction of subducted slabs and plume generation zones in geodynamic models

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Zusammenfassung

Die Interaktion von Prozessen an der Kern-Mantel-Grenze und der Oberfläche ist Gegenstand vieler Untersuchungen der letzten Jahre (z.B. McNamara & Zhong, 2005; Torsvik et al., 2006; Burke et al., 2008; Schubert, 2009; Steinberger & Torsvik, 2012). Ausgelöst wurde dieses Interesse durch Beobachtungen, die eine Korrelation zwischen Hotspots und Plateaubasaltprovinzen auf der einen, sowie Strukturen an der Kern-Mantel-Grenze wie den Rändern der „Large low shear-velocity provinces“ (LLSVPs) auf der anderen Seite zeigen. Die veröffentlichten Arbeiten untersuchen bereits Teile dieser Interaktionen und reproduzieren einzelne Beobachtungen, wie die Entstehung von Plumes an den Rändern von thermo-chemischen Piles. Allerdings gibt es noch keine Modelle, die die beobachtete Hotspot-Verteilung auf der Erde nachvollziehbar reproduzieren, und gleichzeitig mit den weiteren Beobachtungen kompatibel sind.

In dieser Arbeit werden globale Mantelkonvektionsmodelle vorgestellt, die diese Beobachtungen reproduzieren, und gleichzeitig einem quantitativen Vergleich mit der heutigen Hotspot Verteilung standhalten. Die Modelle werden insbesondere bezüglich der Interaktion von subduzierten Platten und den „Plume generation zones“ ausgewertet, was einen Vergleich mit veröffentlichten Hotspot-Katalogen, seismologischen Tomographie-Modellen und Beschränkungen durch Abschätzungen des globalen Erdwärmeflusses und der säkularen Temperaturentwicklung einschließt.

Das vorgestellte und bevorzugte Referenzmodell entwickelt eine Plume-Verteilung und Strukturen an der Kern-Mantel Grenze, die sehr ähnlich zu Beobachtungen auf der Erde ausfallen. Diese Ähnlichkeit wird statistisch ausgewertet und bestätigt. Zusätzlich werden die Plumes durch einen Cluster-Algorithmus untersucht und in zwei Gruppen eingeteilt, die um Afrika und den südlichen Pazifik liegen, und damit nahezu identisch zu beobachteten Hotspots verteilt sind, die mit demselben Algorithmus untersucht wurden. Zusätzlich zeigt der Vergleich mit den seismischen Tomographie-Modellen Savani (Auer et al., 2014) und P07 (Amaru, 2007) deutliche Übereinstimmungen mit dem Konvektionmodell. Eine besonders interessante Übereinstimmung gibt es mit der „Perm“-Anomalie, einer Niedrigkeitgeschwindigkeitszone an der Kern-Mantel-Grenze (Lekic et al., 2012). Diese Zone wurde in bisherigen Modellen trotz ähnlichem Modellsetup nicht reproduziert (z.B. in McNamara & Zhong, 2005; Schubert, 2009; Bower et al., 2013), tritt aber für unser verwendetes Plattenrekonstruktions- und Viskositätsmodell in einem weiten Parameterbereich auf. Schließlich stimmt das Modell auch mit Beobachtungen der thermischen Entwicklung der Manteldurchschnittstemperatur und Oberflächen- und Kern-Mantel-Grenzen Wärmefluss überein.

Eine Sensitivitätsanalyse des Referenzmodells zu den getroffenen Modellannahmen stellt insbesondere die benutzte Plattenrekonstruktion und das Viskositätsmodell als wesentliche Einflussfaktoren auf das Ergebnis heraus. Die Anfangsbedingung spielt zuverlässig nur noch eine geringe Rolle für das Modellergebnis, und nur ungenau bekannte Randbedingungen, wie die Kern-Mantel-Grenzen-Temperatur, spielen keine herausragende Rolle, wobei das Modellergebnis einen mittleren Temperatursprung von $1000 \pm$

200 K favorisiert.

Der zweite große Teil der Arbeit untersucht, ob sich durch die gute Übereinstimmung zwischen Modellen und Beobachtungen für die Randbedingungen getroffene Annahmen validieren und damit das zugrunde liegende Modell verbessert werden kann. Am Beispiel der Phoenix-Gondwana Subduktionszone 200 Ma BP ("before present") wird der Einfluss einer regionalen Änderung an der Plattenrekonstruktion auf das Modellergebnis untersucht. Insbesondere werden Änderungen an der Position der Subduktionszone, der Konvergenzrichtung und der Konvergenzgeschwindigkeit untersucht. Die Modelle zeigen eine starke Abhängigkeit von regionalen tektonischen Prozessen und variieren (regional) beträchtlich aufgrund von 7000 km entfernten Prozessen, die 200 Millionen Jahre in der Vergangenheit statt fanden. Insbesondere die Anzahl und Position von Plumes, und die südlichen Grenzen der afrikanischen LLSVP sind direkt von den getesteten Parametern abhängig. Die Modelle werden in ihrer Kompatibilität zu Beobachtungen bewertet, und zeigen, dass eine Subduktionszone näher an Gondwana, oder ein „flat-slab“ Subduktionsszenario zusammen mit einer möglicherweise um etwa 30 Grad nach Westen rotierten Konvergenzrichtung bessere Übereinstimmungen mit Beobachtungen zeigen, als die originale Plattenrekonstruktion von Seton et al. (2012). Wenn die Subduktionszone vom Kontinent entfernt wird – und damit weiter entfernt im Panthalassa-Ozean liegt – stimmen die Ergebnisse schlecht mit Beobachtungen auf der afrikanischen Hemisphäre überein. Interessanterweise verbessert diese Veränderung den Vergleich zwischen Konvektionsmodell und Tomographie-Modellen auf der pazifischen Hemisphäre. Daher wäre eine zusätzliche, intra-ozeanische Subduktionszone eine mögliche Ergänzung für die Plattenrekonstruktion. Dass die Entdeckung zusätzlicher Subduktionszonen für diese Zeit durch seismische Tomographie möglich ist, zeigt eine Veröffentlichung von van der Meer et al. (2012) in der eine weitere mögliche Subduktionszone im nördlichen Panthalassa Ozean postuliert wird.

Zusammenfassend verbessert diese Arbeit die vorhandenen Methoden der Mantelkonvektionsmodellierung durch die Anwendung eines Viskositätsmodells, das in früheren Arbeiten noch nicht vollständig angewandt wurde. Sie zeigt, dass die derzeitige Hotspot-Verteilung auf der Oberfläche der Erde kein Ergebnis rein zufälliger Konvektionsprozesse ist, sondern eine notwendige Konsequenz von der Interaktion von Paläo-Plattenbewegungen und Prozessen an der Kern-Mantel-Grenze, und dass wir diese Prozesse gut genug verstehen, um den Prozess näherungsweise im Modell nachzubilden. Zusätzlich werden die Möglichkeiten, aber auch die Grenzen der Bestimmung von Paläo-Plattenbewegungen durch Vergleich von Konvektionsmodell und heutigen Beobachtungen aufgezeigt.

Abstract

The interaction of surface and core-mantle boundary processes have been investigated in numerous studies in recent years (e.g. McNamara & Zhong, 2005; Torsvik et al., 2006; Burke et al., 2008; Schuberth, 2009; Steinberger & Torsvik, 2012). The interest in this topic was raised by observations like the correlation between hotspots, reconstructed large igneous provinces and erupted kimberlites, and core-mantle boundary structures. While these studies already prove the existence and reproduce single observations of these links, they fail in providing a convincing match to the observed hotspot distribution on Earth. In this work, models of global mantle convection with prescribed surface plate motions are developed. In particular, they are set up to test the possibility of creating a present-day state of the models that is comparable to present-day Earth observations. A special focus is laid on the interaction of subducted slabs and plume generation zones at the core-mantle boundary, which is investigated and compared to surface observations like published hotspot catalogues, seismic observations like global tomographies and constraints from temperature evolution and heat flow measurements. The preferred reference model develops an Earth-like distribution of plumes and zones of low seismic velocity at the core-mantle boundary. This similarity is proven to be statistically significant. The plumes are separated by a clustering algorithm into two groups around Africa and the South Pacific, which is nearly identical to the separation of observed hotspots. Furthermore, the comparison to seismic tomography at the core-mantle boundary shows large congruency between the mantle convection model and the tomography models Savani (Auer et al., 2014) and P07 (Amaru, 2007). An especially convincing agreement exists in the description of the seismologically observed "Perm" anomaly (Lekic et al., 2012), which is reproduced for a wide range of model parameters, and has not been reproduced in previous convection models with similar setup (e.g. McNamara & Zhong, 2005; Schuberth, 2009; Bower et al., 2013). The model further matches thermal constraints and observations of the Earth like the secular cooling rate and the surface and core-mantle boundary heat flux.

In a sensitivity analysis of the model results to assumed material properties, initial and boundary conditions, strong dependencies on the assumed viscosity formulation and surface plate reconstruction are shown, while the influence of the initial condition is minor. The investigated model results are insensitive to uncertain boundary conditions like the core-mantle boundary temperature, with a preference of the model towards a core-mantle boundary temperature jump of 1000 ± 200 K.

The second part of the thesis investigates the possibility to constrain a plate reconstruction on the basis of the fit between convection model, seismic tomography and hotspot positions. On the example of the Phoenix-Gondwana subduction zone around 200 Ma BP (before present), the influence of a regional change of subduction zone position, convergence velocity and convergence direction is tested. The models show a strong influence of the regional subduction zone setup on the present-day mantle state. The number and position of plumes, and the boundaries of the large-low velocity province

beneath Africa are directly affected by the changes. The models are ranked according to their fit to present-day observations and suggest a closer subduction to Gondwana, or a flat-slab subduction scenario, with a possibly slightly oblique convergence direction. A subduction far out in the Panthalassa ocean does not fit observations in the African hemisphere, but improves the LLSVP position in the Pacific hemisphere, and might therefore be investigated in further studies as an additional intra-oceanic subduction zone.

In summary, this thesis provides progress in the methods of mantle convection modelling by using a temperature-dependent viscosity formulation not investigated before. It shows that the resulting plume distribution is more Earth-like compared to other approaches, and a necessary consequence of the interaction of paleo-plate movements and processes at the core-mantle boundary. Additionally, it explores the possibility to constrain paleo-plate reconstructions by forward numerical modelling.

Contents

Zusammenfassung	3
Abstract	5
1. Plume-Plate Interaction in Earth's Mantle Convection	11
1.1. Heterogeneities at the Core-Mantle Boundary	11
1.2. History of the Plume Hypothesis	11
1.3. Seismic Observations	12
1.4. Geochemical and Petrological Constraints	14
1.5. Previous Convection Modelling Results	17
1.6. Synthesis	19
2. Theory of Mantle Convection Modelling	21
2.1. Basics of Numerical Geodynamic Modelling	21
2.1.1. Motivation	21
2.1.2. Equations	21
2.2. Basics of CitcomS	24
2.2.1. Numerical Techniques	24
2.2.2. Modifications of CitcomS	27
2.2.3. Extensibility and Reusability	28
2.3. Model Setup	28
2.3.1. Initial Conditions	28
2.3.2. Boundary Conditions	32
2.3.3. Using Thermodynamic Databases for Material Properties	33
2.3.4. Viscosity Description	37
2.3.5. List of Models	40
2.4. Interpreting Model Results	44
2.4.1. Spatial Point Set Distributions	44
2.4.2. Spatial Clustering	46
2.4.3. Hotspot Catalogue	48
2.4.4. Seismic Tomography	50
3. The Influence of Global Plate Movements on Mantle Plumes	53
3.1. Resulting Plume Distribution	53
3.1.1. Time Evolution of Reference Model	53
3.1.2. Model Plume Distribution and Earth's Hotspot Distribution	55
3.1.3. Plume and Hotspot Clustering	58
3.2. Model Parameter Sensitivity	58
3.2.1. Core-Mantle Boundary Temperature Jump	58
3.2.2. Viscosity Profile	61

3.2.3. Material Description	64
3.2.4. Initial Condition of Temperature	64
3.2.5. Initial Condition of Composition	68
3.3. Model Properties and Validating Observations	69
3.3.1. Seismic Tomography	69
3.3.2. South Atlantic Observations	73
3.3.3. Pile Area	76
3.3.4. CMB Velocity Skewness	81
3.3.5. Slab Sinking Rate	82
3.3.6. Temperature and Heat Flux Evolution	84
4. Testing Plate Reconstructions with Mantle Convection Modelling	89
4.1. Motivation	89
4.2. Plate Reconstruction Scenarios	89
4.2.1. Subduction Zone Position	90
4.2.2. Reference Frame Rotation	93
4.2.3. Convergence Velocity	95
4.2.4. Convergence Direction	95
4.3. Excluding Setups	98
5. Conclusion	101
6. Outlook	103
Selbstständigkeitserklärung	107
Acknowledgements	109
List of Figures	111
Bibliography	113
A. Data	125
A.1. Hotspot Catalogue	125
B. Models	127
B.1. Additional Figures	127
B.2. Model Summaries	133
Curriculum Vitae	161
List of Publications	163

1. Plume-Plate Interaction in Earth's Mantle Convection

1.1. Heterogeneities at the Core-Mantle Boundary

The surface of the Earth is a classical region to investigate. The reasons for this focus are numerous: Life and all processes that are affected by it are restricted to the uppermost ~ 10 km of the Earth. The interplay between lithosphere, hydrosphere and atmosphere lead to many interesting processes including solid-fluid-gas interactions, phase transitions, and chemical and thermal exchange between different reservoirs. However, another surface on Earth features most of these complex interactions - apart from life - and that is the core-mantle boundary. Most interesting processes at this surface are: Interaction of liquid core phases with solid mantle phases, buoyancy differences causing a topography, a significant heat flux through the surface, phase transitions of several kinds (solid-state phase transitions in the mantle material as well as possible partial melting in the ultra-low velocity zones, ULVZs). The large distance to the surface and opacity of Earth's mantle to most observation techniques limit the observables that are available to investigate these processes. Therefore, numerical modelling has become a vital tool for studying the deeper regions of the Earth. Nonetheless, there are observations, in particular seismic methods and geochemical constraints, that are able to shed light on some of the ongoing CMB processes. Both - observations and models - will be summarized in this chapter to provide an overview over the topic of this thesis. Because the concept of mantle plumes is an essential idea for the rest of this thesis, the following section will start with an overview about its history.

1.2. History of the Plume Hypothesis

Probably the first explanation of a different source mechanism for intraplate volcanism often occurring on ocean islands than for regular plate-boundary volcanism was stated by Wilson (1963). He suggested a deeper seated, relatively immobile source region for hotspots, to combine the observation of relative stability of hotspots with the concept of moving plates and a convecting mantle. In his work, however, the source region was assumed to lie in the center of convection cells, an idea that has been revised by Morgan (1971) to the general region of the lower mantle. He proposed the idea of mantle plumes, localized regions of hot upwelling material that spread radially beneath the lithosphere. However, Morgan assumed that the plumes would "provide the driving force of plate tectonics", an idea that has been discarded in the meantime (Davies, 1988; Sleep, 1990). Still, the question if and how much plumes affect individual plate motions has not been settled up to today (e.g. van Hinsbergen et al., 2011; Cande & Stegman, 2011). Therefore, existing models and findings concerning the behaviour of slabs and mantle plumes will be presented in Subsection 1.5.

Convincing seismological evidence for or against the existence of mantle plumes, and especially their extent in the lower mantle, has been relatively rare until the last two decades. Available resolution of seismic studies – together with the fact that small, seismically slow regions are hard to detect – have been only overcome by newly developed techniques like in Montelli et al. (2004). However, the comparison of seismology and convection models has provided good constraints on general features of mantle convection, like the non-existence of a mid-mantle boundary layer (Jordan et al., 1993). This supported the idea of plumes originating at the core-mantle boundary (CMB), since it is the only possible source for their excess temperature. The construction of global tomography models later revealed the existence of two large regions of reduced shear-velocity at the core-mantle boundary (LLSVPs) and the correlation of these regions to surface observations of plumes and large igneous provinces (LIPs) suggests a tight connection to plume generation (Torsvik et al., 2006; Burke et al., 2008). Further details of seismic constraints are discussed in Subsection 1.3.

Additionally, it has been a long known fact that hotspot volcanism produces magmas with significantly different geochemical signatures than plate-boundary volcanism and that this change occurs gradually at mid-ocean ridges towards hotspot locations (e.g. Schilling, 1973; Hart et al., 1973). Therefore, already in the 1980's the geochemical data was interpreted to show a recycling of previously molten material through subduction and mantle plumes (White & Hofmann, 1982; Hofmann & White, 1982). Today, important differences that distinguish ocean-island basalts (OIBs) from mid-ocean ridge basalts (MORBs) can be found in the major element composition, trace element composition, radiogenic isotope ratios and noble gas isotope ratios (White, 2010), and their constraints will be discussed in Subsection 1.4.

1.3. Seismic Observations

In global seismic tomography models of the mantle, two large regions of lower than average seismic velocities – in particular shear-wave velocities – are observed (Dziewonski et al., 1977; Su & Dziewonski, 1997) and confirmed and refined in newer studies (Ritsema, 1999; Kustowski et al., 2008; Simmons et al., 2009; Auer et al., 2014). These regions lie beneath Africa and the South Pacific, and if the -1 % shear-wave velocity contour in the SMEAN tomography model (Becker & Boschi, 2002) is considered their boundary, they contain 1.6 vol% and 1.9 mass% of Earth's mantle and cover around 21% of the CMB area (Burke et al., 2008). As mentioned above many surface hotspots and large igneous provinces overly these regions as shown in Figure 1.1, and therefore they deserve special attention in this thesis as a possible "plume generation zone" (Burke et al., 2008; Torsvik et al., 2010).

Connected to the existence of these regions seems the observation that the distribution of seismic S-wave velocity anomalies close to the core-mantle boundary appears to be bimodal, in which a gaussian distribution is overlain by an excursion at low velocities (Hernlund & Houser, 2008). This feature is distinct for S-velocities and not present in P-velocities for which a single gaussian distribution is observed. The integrated volume of the additional excursion is estimated to be around 2.0 ± 0.4 % of Earth's mantle volume, which is very compatible with the 1.6 vol% from the two antipodal LLSVPs. Due to this difference between S- and P-velocities the attribution of the anomalies to

Fig. 1.1 : Figure of Torsvik et al. (2010) showing a map view of the SMEAN tomography model (Becker & Boschi, 2002) at 2800 km depth with seismically identified hotspots (Montelli et al., 2004), and reconstructed large igneous provinces and kimberlite eruption positions. The occurrence of two regions of low seismic shear wave velocity is illustrated by the -1 % δV_S outline (red). Present-day continents are shown for geographical reference.

purely higher temperatures seems at least questionable.

In fact, several studies argue that these regions consist of chemically different material for a number of reasons, of which only the seismological ones will be mentioned in this section. In general, the root-mean-square values for the ratio ξ between bulk-sound- and Vs-anomalies are thought to depend only on pressure (hence depth) in the case of purely thermal heterogeneities in the mantle. However, in the lowermost mantle there are strong lateral variations in this ratio (van der Hilst, 1999), which is interpreted as evidence for compositional heterogeneity. Additionally, Ni et al. (2002) showed that the side of the African LLSVP is very sharp, in their model with a velocity drop of around 3% over 50 km. Combined with the modelled outwards tilt of the boundary of the LLSVP they state that this can only be achieved by a compositional layer in their convection modelling study. On the other hand Wang & Wen (2007) find the boundary to be tilted in the usual bell-shape geometry and the lower part of the anomaly has a negative velocity anomaly of around 5%, which is decreasing to around 2-3 % in the mid-mantle. Nevertheless, also the observation of increased density in these regions favours a thermo-chemical interpretation (e.g. Ishii & Tromp, 1999; Deschamps & Trampert, 2003).

1.4. Geochemical and Petrological Constraints

In this subsection, the geochemical and petrological constraints on the interaction of subducted slabs and mantle plumes will be discussed. It is largely based on White (2010), but extended by newer publications relevant for this thesis.

The major element composition of magmatic rocks – that means the ratios of the most abundant elements – can be used to classify them into categories depending on their concentrations of silica or alkaline components. For the purpose of the investigation of slab-plume interaction it would be most valuable to be able to characterize the source rocks of mid-ocean ridge basalt (MORB) and ocean-island basalt (OIB). However, the process to reconstruct the source rock of a magmatic rock is a complex procedure with a number of uncertainties, as for example the degree of partial melting and the process of fractional crystallization during the evolution of the melt as well as the process of partial melting itself. Herzberg et al. (2007) provide a detailed explanation of the necessary procedures to reconstruct the source rock of a magmatic product. An interesting consequence of this process is the determination of the approximate potential temperature of the source rock via melt evolution modelling. In Herzberg & Asimow (2008) hotspot magmas have potential temperatures around 100 - 250 K hotter than the average mantle that produces MORB, and according to this study, this melting can not be caused by volatile enrichment alone.

In addition to the elevated temperature, ocean island basalts show distinctively different trace-element patterns compared to mid-ocean ridge basalts, as is shown in Figure 1.2. In particular, the abundance of incompatible trace elements is much higher and increases with incompatibility. While, in general, an enrichment in incompatible elements can be achieved by creating melts with a very low degree of partial melting, the above presented conclusion of major-element compositions suggests a higher plume temperature and therefore larger melt fractions in ocean-island basalts. Thus, a likely explanation for the ratios is the assumption that the source material of hotspot magmas

Fig. 1.2 : Spider diagram by White (2010) showing the concentrations of trace elements in MORB and different OIBs. The elements are ordered by increasing compatibility and the concentrations are normalized by the bulk Earth ratios (McDonough & Sun, 1995). Representative patterns are plotted for MORB, Hawaii (Tanaka & Nakamura, 2005), the Canary Islands (Lundstrom et al., 2003), St. Helena (Willbold & Stracke, 2006, an example of a HIMU, high- μ or $^{238}\text{U}/^{204}\text{Pb}$ OIB), Tristan da Cunha (Willbold & Stracke, 2006), Pitcairn (Willbold & Stracke, 2006, example of EM I – enriched mantle I – OIB), Samoa (Jackson et al., 2007), and the Society Islands (Hauri & Hart, 1997, example of EM II – enriched mantle II – OIB). All OIBs show a much higher concentration of incompatible elements compared to the MORB composition.

Fig. 1.3 : Isotope plot by White (2010, modified) showing ϵ_{Nd} (the isotope deviation of Nd) versus $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$. The data is taken from the GEOROC database (<http://georoc.mpch-mainz.gwdg.de/georoc/>) and the gray field for MORB is based on the PetDB database (<http://www.petdb.org>). The additional black circle shows the original MORB definition by Zindler & Hart (1986). Many OIBs plot outside of the MORB field, and most MORBs that extend the gray field to the bottom-right were sampled close to hotspot positions.

already underwent a process of enrichment at the surface, was subducted and recycled by mantle plumes (White & Hofmann, 1982; Hofmann & White, 1982). White (2010) additionally argues that melting in the lower mantle (e.g. close to the core-mantle boundary) would cause significantly different patterns of enrichment, and the observed pattern can therefore only be explained by surface melting. However, newer work by Herzberg et al. (2013) challenge this interpretation, by stating that the elevated Helium isotopes and higher Nickel content of mantle plume sources could be derived from a reservoir that was formed as part of a basal magma ocean, solidifying at the core-mantle boundary.

Furthermore, radiogenic isotope patterns of plume-derived hotspot magmas distinguish them from average MORB, as shown in Figure 1.3 in the case of ^{143}Nd variations against $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ variations. In fact, samples from Samoa presented by Jackson et al. (2007) display values of $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ as high as 0.7204 and ϵ_{Nd} as low as -6, which plots outside of Figure 1.3. According to White (2010), these values are more extreme than any modern

Pacific sediment, and the conclusion of Jackson et al. (2007) is therefore to assume a significant amount of subducted ancient sediment within plumes of the EM II class.

The spatial distribution of isotope patterns is another way to constrain plume generation processes. Weis et al. (2011) for example state that the difference between the two volcanic lines of Hawaii may show the systematic heterogeneity of the plume's source material relative to its origin at the core-mantle boundary. She assumes a radiogenic isotope enrichment in the Pacific LLSVP to be the source for the Loa trend, reaching further into the direction of the EM I class of hotspots (see Figure 1.3 for classification). Similar, but less clear patterns have also been reported for Samoa and the Marquesas (Huang et al., 2011), although the spatial correlation to the LLSVP seems less clear in these cases.

For many years, the elevated $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ ratios in hotspot magmas have served as an argument for a deep undegassed reservoir as the source region of mantle plumes (Allègre, 1982; Allègre et al., 1987). While ^3He is not produced in significant amounts by processes on the Earth, ^4He is generated by alpha decay of heavier radioactive elements and much more abundant in Earth's atmosphere. These isotopes are degassed from erupted magma and most of them stay in the atmosphere or get lost into space without being transported back into the mantle. Therefore, a high ratio of ^3He isotopes argues towards a deep-mantle hidden reservoir that has not been degassed before and is relatively isolated from the rest of the mantle. When newer studies showed that the He ratios at best weakly correlate with other isotope ratios, and additionally significant amounts of He can remain within partially molten parent rock, this line of arguments has been weakened. However, other noble gas isotope ratios such as $^{129}\text{Xe}/^{130}\text{Xe}$ and $^{20}\text{Ne}/^{22}\text{Ne}$ in hotspot magmas are different from MORB samples as well (Mukhopadhyay, 2012). In particular, this study argues towards a creation of these heterogeneities at latest 100 Ma after Earth's early differentiation. If these ratios have their source within the LLSVPs, they must be very long-lived features and can not be exclusively explained by accumulated subducted oceanic crust.

While ocean-island basalts therefore significantly differ from normal mid-ocean ridge basalts, the discussion about their possible origins does not seem to be settled. In fact White (2010) states:

"In summary, there is little consensus on the origin of the geochemical signatures of mantle plumes. A variety of ideas has been proposed, yet none seems entirely satisfactory. The common thread of all these ideas is, however, creation of heterogeneity in Earth's lithosphere and recycling of this material into the deep mantle through subduction and mantle convection."

A noteworthy idea, which has been explicitly stated by Tackley (2012) and will be discussed in the next section, is therefore, that the search for a single source mechanism might not be successful if multiple mechanisms exist that contribute to the observations with varying degree.

1.5. Previous Convection Modelling Results

A number of studies has investigated the potential influences and consequences of slab-plume interaction on regional and global scales. These works can be divided into three categories of plume-slab interaction: Influence of subducting slabs on plume generation

at the CMB; Plume-slab interaction of a rising plume with a sinking slab (e.g. subducting farallon slab and "yellowstone plume"); Plume-slab interaction at the surface (e.g. Deccan traps, influence on plate movement). Since this thesis focuses on the global scale and on plume generation, only the most important models of the first point will be summarized here. Interpretations of other models will be mentioned throughout the thesis, where appropriate. For a number of relevant models on smaller scales the reader is referred to Tackley (2011); Tan et al. (2002).

Investigating the interaction of subducted slabs and core-mantle boundary processes involves large-scale, whole mantle convection models. Because the computational cost of global high-resolution models like Stadler et al. (2010) is too high to solve for longer timespans, the models in this thesis are limited to a resolution that is sufficient to capture the general slab evolution and convection flow patterns. A review of relevant processes visible in high-resolution small-scale convection models is given in Billen (2008). However, there are a number of studies investigating similar processes as this study on a similar global scale. McNamara & Zhong (2005) showed that incorporating Earth's subduction history into convection models leads to the creation of thermo-chemical piles at the CMB that approximately satisfy geometrical constraints from seismic tomography. Their study however, was limited to a plate reconstruction that reaches 119 Ma back in time and the resulting shapes deviate regionally quite significantly from seismic tomography. Follow-up studies on these models (Ritsema et al., 2007; Bull et al., 2009) compared the resulting seismic velocity field to tomography results by applying a resolution filter operator appropriate to the seismic tomography model used. They also extend the conversion from temperature and chemistry to seismic velocity from a constant conversion factor to the use of thermodynamic databases by Stixrude & Lithgow-Bertelloni (2005). In these studies the thermo-chemical convection models were found to better resemble the long-wavelength seismic tomography structures than purely thermal convection, although the overall statistical comparison of amplitude and character of anomalies is relatively similar. In a separate set of models with similar methodology, Schubert et al. (2009b) showed that purely thermal models may resemble the seismic tomography equally well or even better when the CMB temperature jump is considered to be relatively high (1000-1500 K). However, their models do not incorporate temperature-dependent viscosity, which could change flow patterns significantly. In a follow-up study, Davies et al. (2012) extended this investigation to also account for weak temperature-dependent viscosity (a factor of 100 weaker than in McNamara & Zhong (2005)), and different compositions of the chemical pile. They also state that for this combination of high core-mantle boundary temperature and weakly temperature-dependent viscosity the thermal model seems to fit the data better compared to seismic tomography than the thermo-chemical model.

Steinberger & Torsvik (2012) published global convection models in which plumes get preferentially created at the edges of thermo-chemical piles in a realistic pattern. These models do not include temperature-dependent viscosity and no quantitative comparison between model plumes and hotspot positions, however they create a realistic pattern of plume formation by the inclusion of 300 Ma of subduction history. Following the results of Tan et al. (2011), Bower et al. (2013) created models of thermo-chemical convection with chemically distinct material that features a higher than average bulk modulus. This property leads to the generation of steep pile edges and plumes that preferentially form close to these edges (Tan et al., 2011) but are also difficult to maintain stable over

Fig. 1.4 : Schematics showing the widely used concept of mantle convection in an exemplary slice through the South Atlantic. Subducting slabs reach the core-mantle boundary and hot plumes rise from thermal boundary layer at the core-mantle boundary. Dense material could accumulate in the form of thermochemical piles (a), but independent of this process, plumes will entrain and recycle subducted material (a,b).

timespans longer than a few hundred million years.

Bull et al. (2014) tried to exploit the advances in plate reconstructions back in time to 450 Ma, which was so far done only in very approximate plate reconstructions (Zhang et al., 2010). They find that the LLSVPs would be stable for this time span, if they had existed in approximately their current-day configuration. Additionally they show that a purely Pacific LLSVP would not split up during the existence of Pangea, as was proposed in earlier studies (Zhong et al., 2007; Zhang et al., 2010).

1.6. Synthesis

Mantle plumes have been thought to be the source of hotspot volcanism in many works. Most of them probably originate at the CMB, especially at the borders of Large Low Shear Velocity Provinces (LLSVPs), which are considered a prominent feature at that depth. During the upwelling the plumes undergo several changes due to compressibility (Tan & Gurnis, 2005), phase transitions (Hirose, 2002) or the interaction with subducting slabs and large-scale mantle convection (Jellinek & Manga, 2004). The recent hotspot positions and reconstructed large igneous provinces and kimberlite eruption sites cluster around the borders of two large-low-shear-velocity provinces near the core-mantle boundary (Burke et al., 2008). Connected with the observation that regions of recent or ancient subduction in general lack hotspots, this is a strong evidence for tight links between surface and deep mantle processes.

Figure 1.4 emerges out of the previously discussed observations and models. Mantle convection is mostly driven by subducting slabs that descend through the mantle, with possible temporary interruptions at the mantle transition zone, until they reach the core-mantle boundary. Heat from the core creates a bottom thermal boundary layer that rises in the form of plumes. These plumes entrain a part of the subducted material and, possibly, remaining primordial material. The existence and composition of thermochemical piles at the CMB remains somewhat debated, but they do provide solutions for a number of observations, in particular, if considering the possibility of a mixture of

materials in these regions as proposed in Tackley (2012). Although the origin of the piles remains unclear, the general consensus leans towards a thermo-chemical interpretation, although the possibility of a predominantly thermal origin remains. Independent of this discussion the presence of plumes reaching the surface at least at some of current days hotspot positions is largely accepted and supported by increasing evidence. But although the correlation of deep mantle structures with mantle convection models seems convincing (McNamara & Zhong, 2005; Bull et al., 2014) and there are suggestions for creating plumes at the boundaries of thermo-chemical piles (Tan et al., 2011; Steinberger & Torsvik, 2012) there is no quantitative comparison of the position of plumes rising from the edges of thermo-chemical piles in convection models and observed hotspot positions. This thesis aims to fill this gap, following the conclusion of Tackley (2012):

"Future progress in understanding the deep mantle will require advanced modelling to understand present-day structure in the context of long-term evolution, which will in turn require better knowledge of the relevant mineral physics properties. Seismological observations of increasing resolution will continue to play a key role in unravelling present-day structures."

2. Theory of Mantle Convection Modelling

2.1. Basics of Numerical Geodynamic Modelling

2.1.1. Motivation

Studying mantle convection poses a number of significant challenges that limit its accessibility in observation-driven and analogue-modelling-driven research. The long timespans usually restrict observations to a snapshot of current-day convection, which complicates investigating time-dependent processes, e.g. the stability of convection features. Additionally, the very large length scales force analogue modellers to scale their experiments by many orders of magnitude, which makes the extrapolation a difficult task. Moreover, realistic material properties include a dependence on many quantities, like temperature, pressure, strain rate or history of strain, and not all of these complexities can be handled in analogue models. Numerical modelling is able to overcome some of these limitations and provide hypotheses about parameter ranges and processes that are not accessible in analogue modelling or observations. In particular, the control over the model setup allows to isolate dependencies and their effect on the overall convection, without the complexity of additional influences. Of course, the generated predictions need to be validated with available observations to verify their plausibility.

In the following sections the approximations and models that are employed in this thesis are described. Additionally, the methods used to compare the models with observations will be discussed.

2.1.2. Equations

In general, the equations describing the motion and thermal evolution of a fluid can be stated as the conservation of mass, momentum and energy (Schubert et al., 2001):

$$\rho_{,t} + (\rho u_i)_{,i} = 0, \quad (2.1)$$

$$\rho \frac{Du_i}{Dt} = -p_{,i} + \tau_{ij,j} + \rho g_i, \quad (2.2)$$

$$\rho T \frac{Ds}{Dt} = \tau_{ij} u_{i,j} + (kT_{,i})_{,i} + \rho H. \quad (2.3)$$

Hereby ρ is density, t is time, u velocity, and i and j subscripts are indicating spatial components of vectors, with the expression $A_{,y}$ representing the partial derivative of A with respect to y . $\frac{DA}{Dt}$ represents the material derivative of A with respect to y . p denotes the pressure, τ shear stress, g gravitational acceleration, T is used for temperature, s for entropy, k for thermal conductivity, and H is the specific heat production rate. The

equations above are stated in their strong form for an infinitesimal fluid parcel. In their integral / weak form the global conservation of mass, momentum and energy will depend on the applied boundary conditions. For the application to the mantle, both surface and core-mantle boundary are assumed to have negligible material or stress exchange, therefore fulfilling Equations 2.1 and 2.2, however this neglects, for example, the loss of volatiles at plate boundaries and intraplate volcanism. Nevertheless, the driving energy of convection on Earth is thermal energy that enters and leaves the mantle in the form of heatflux. It influences the conservation of thermal energy within the mantle, and via the coupled nature of the equations – in particular because of $\rho(T)$ and the low thermal conductivity – also drives convection.

For the application to mantle convection, all above equations can be simplified significantly, when considering material and geometrical properties of the mantle. It is assumed that density changes from a depth-dependent reference state are small (at most on the order of percent), the movements are slow (compared to elastic/sound waves in rocks), and the diffusion of stress is much faster than the diffusion of thermal energy. Additionally, self-gravitation of density anomalies is neglected, and a purely radial gravitational acceleration is employed. Finally, the thermal conductivity is assumed to be almost constant ($k_{,i} \ll k$). These approximations lead to the equations implemented in CitcomS, the software that will be used for most models of this thesis.

Equations 2.4 to 2.7 are taken from the original CitcomS documentation and later on simplified further to the specific application cases that were investigated in this thesis. Authorship remains with the authors of the original form, while the modifications and additional derivations are part of this thesis.

CitcomS treats the mantle as an anelastic, compressible, viscous spherical shell applying the Truncated Anelastic Liquid Approximation as described above. With these simplifications, the equations for conservation of mass, momentum, and energy are:

$$(\rho u_i)_{,i} = 0, \quad (2.4)$$

$$-P_{,i} + \left(\eta(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i} - \frac{2}{3}u_{k,k}\delta_{ij}) \right)_{,i} - \delta\rho g\delta_{ir} = 0, \quad (2.5)$$

$$\rho c_P (T_{,t} + u_i T_{,i}) = \rho c_P \kappa T_{,ii} - \rho \alpha g u_r T + \Phi + \rho (Q_{L,t} + u_i Q_{L,i}) + \rho H, \quad (2.6)$$

where P is the dynamic pressure, η is the viscosity, δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta tensor, $\delta\rho$ is the density anomaly, r is the radial direction, c_P is the heat capacity, κ is the thermal diffusivity, α is the thermal expansivity, Φ is the viscous dissipation, and Q_L is the latent heat due to phase transitions.

With phase transitions and temperature and composition variations, the density anomalies are defined as:

$$\delta\rho = -\alpha\bar{\rho}(T - \bar{T}_a) + \delta\rho_{ph}\Gamma + \delta\rho_{ch}C, \quad (2.7)$$

where $\bar{\rho}$ is the radial profile of density, \bar{T}_a is the radial profile of adiabatic temperature, $\delta\rho_{ph}$ is the density jump across a phase transition, $\delta\rho_{ch}$ is the density difference between the compositions, Γ is the phase function (fraction of material that already underwent the phase transition), and C is the composition.

In the further course of this thesis these equations are simplified to the following case, in which the effects of compressibility, shear heating, adiabatic heating and phase transitions are neglected following the Boussinesq approximation:

$$u_{i,i} = 0 \tag{2.8}$$

$$-P_{,i} + (\eta(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}))_{,i} - \delta\rho g \delta_{ir} = 0, \tag{2.9}$$

$$\rho c_P (T_{,t} + u_i T_{,i}) = \rho c_P \kappa T_{,ii} + \rho H. \tag{2.10}$$

However, the computation of $\delta\rho$ will be extended by the use of a property table computed by the thermodynamic database software `Perple_X` (Connolly, 2005, see also Subsection 2.3.3), in which case Equation 2.7 will become the following:

$$\delta\rho = \delta\rho(P, T, \mathbf{C}). \tag{2.11}$$

In this approach, density changes due to phase transitions are not only incorporated for the usually considered olivine–spinel–perovskite–post-perovskite phase system but also for phase transitions like coesite–stishovite or the often neglected decomposition of garnet into different perovskite- and periclase-phases around 700 km depth. This is especially important when considering the fact that Earth’s mantle consists of chemically heterogeneous material and these phase boundaries depend on the mineral compositions of these materials (Tronnes, 2010; Xu et al., 2008).

An interesting consequence of the reformulation of Equation 2.11 is the fact that α is not required any more in the Equations 2.8 to 2.10, since it is only used implicitly to calculate ρ , and these calculations are executed in `Perple_X`.

To calculate the density difference $\delta\rho$, a method to trace the composition \mathbf{C} within the model domain is required. `CitcomS` employs a tracer approach, distributing particles throughout the domain that carry a compositional flavour and are advected with the flow field.

All equations are solved in a non-dimensional parametrization replacing the dimensional quantities. Therefore, the magnitudes of velocities and pressure are comparable and the system becomes easier to solve numerically. Additionally, in the simplest cases the models can be characterized by non-dimensional numbers like the Rayleigh-number, which scales with the proportion of convective to conductive heat transport in the model and therefore can be seen as a measure for the ‘vigor’ of the convection. The thermal Rayleigh number in `CitcomS` is defined as:

$$Ra = \frac{\rho_0 g_0 \alpha_0 \Delta T R_0^3}{\eta_0 \kappa_0} \quad (2.12)$$

Although the models created within this thesis are locally far more complicated than the simple definition of the Rayleigh number can describe, it is nonetheless used as an input parameter for the models to determine the temperature contrast across the model domain. However, due to the additional dependencies of ρ, g, α, η and κ on temperature, pressure and position, the actual local convection regime might be far different from what is suggested by this global Rayleigh number. In any place throughout this thesis the Rayleigh number is used to characterize a model setup, it is calculated with R_0 being the Earth's radius (the usual notation of CitcomS) and the reference values for all other quantities, which are set as model constants as described in Table 2.2.

2.2. Basics of CitcomS

2.2.1. Numerical Techniques

CitcomS is a highly parallelized and widely used code for simulating Earth's convection in the mantle in a three-dimensional spherical shell. It is supported and distributed as an open-source code by the Computational Infrastructure for Geodynamics (CIG, www.geodynamics.org). The different modules of CitcomS were created over a period of around twenty years of development and published in several articles, for example Zhong et al. (2000), Tan et al. (2006) and McNamara & Zhong (2004). The code is benchmarked for instantaneous and time-dependent convection (Zhong et al., 2008). The applied numerical techniques are, as described in the CitcomS manual (Tan et al., 2009).

CitcomS discretizes the equations derived in Section 2.1.2 by applying a finite element method (Hughes, 1987). All equations are solved on hexahedral (brick) elements, which are linear in velocity and temperature and have an element-wise constant pressure (Q1P0). It employs the Uzawa algorithm for solving the Stokes equations by iterating over the momentum and mass conservation equations (Moresi & Gurnis, 1996; Ramage & Wathen, 1994). The temperature equation is solved with a Streamline-Upwind Petrov-Galerkin approach (Brooks, 1981). The model domain is decomposed into 12 diamond shaped caps, which are divided regularly into n^3 elements ($n \in \mathbb{N}$). Each cap is usually assigned to a different compute core, however, the caps can be further subdivided, so that the possible number of compute cores for a model run is equal to $2^x * 12$ ($x \in \mathbb{N}$, see Figure 2.1). For all presented models x was chosen to equal 3, resulting in 96 compute cores, or 8 nodes on a cluster with 12 cores per node. The averaged compute time per model of 10,000 core hours was therefore distributed to 96 cores, resulting in a runtime of around 100 hours.

The tracking of composition is implemented as a tracer-ratio method (McNamara & Zhong, 2004), utilizing a predictor-corrector integration scheme for tracer movement. Each tracer carries a compositional scalar, and the ratio of tracers of different flavours in neighbouring elements is used to calculate an averaged composition at the mesh node locations. For accurate compositional tracking the later on presented models use 50

Fig. 2.1 : CitcomS separates the 3D model sphere into 12 diamond shaped caps (shown is an orthographic projection from the CitcomS manual by Tan et al. (2009)). Each cap can be separated further and distributed across several compute cores. In this example, every cap is divided into 4×4 subdomains. Assuming a radial splitting of 2 domains this would result in $12 \times 4 \times 4 \times 2 = 384$ cores.

tracers per mesh cell, resulting in a total number of 150 million tracers in roughly 3 million cells.

Solver tolerance

Due to the application of an iterative solver, Equations 2.8, 2.9 and 2.10 are only solved approximately, up to a tolerance level for the remaining residual. This tolerance is defined as model input parameter and influences the numerical accuracy and computational cost of each model run. In particular, the residual tolerance of the Stokes system drastically influences the computational cost up to an order of magnitude of computing time within reasonable tolerance ranges. However, it is not straightforward to calculate the necessary accuracy for one particular model setup. Because the necessary 3D CitcomS model series with varying tolerance levels would have consumed an unnecessary large amount of computing time, a series of test models was run with the code ASPECT (Kronbichler et al., 2012), which allows for cheap computations in 2D, while using the same overall setup as the 3D CitcomS models. Although the computation of residuals between ASPECT and CitcomS differs slightly, the formulation is very similar, and therefore the results are assumed to be transferable. The results will then be compared and the highest possible tolerance, which does not affect the important model features, will be considered the optimal tolerance level for further models. In this thesis, these are mainly the position of generated plumes and the shape of subducted slabs and rising plumes.

The results of this model series are shown in Figure 2.2. While increasing the solver

Fig. 2.2 : The modelled temperature field after 250 million years of convection in 2D for different solver tolerances computed with the mantle convection code ASPECT. Increasing the accuracy improves the solution up to a tolerance of $1e-4$, a lower tolerance does not affect the solution visibly.

Fig. 2.3 : The required model runtime plotted over the solver tolerance for the Stokes system. Increasing the tolerance up to 10^{-3} reduces the runtime significantly. Further increasing the tolerance leads to an inaccurate solution, which increases the required number of Stokes iterations, and leads to convergence failure for a tolerance of 10^{-2} .

tolerance from the ASPECT default value of $1e-7$ (CitcomS utilizes a default of $1e-4$) to a value of $1e-4$ does not produce visible changes to the solution, it reduces the computing time by nearly a factor of 4, as can be seen in Figure 2.3. Because of the different code, and the 2D instead of 3D geometry, this gain is not directly transferable to the CitcomS models, but the gain is likely to be at least as high, probably higher. The relaxation from $1e-4$ to $1e-3$ shows first changes to small scale features in the solution; however, the fixed surface boundary conditions keep the solution from changing too drastically, and the position and shape of slabs and plumes remains very similar. This change decrease the required computing time by another 15%. Noticeable differences consist in the slightly different timing of plume arrival as observed in Figure 2.2 in the upper right sector of panel $1e-3$ and $1e-4$. When increasing the tolerance to $5e-3$, the position and general shape of subducted slabs still remain similar, but the slab behaviour at the core-mantle boundary as well as the position and shape of rising plumes experience serious changes. In particular, the difference in plume position and shape make this tolerance level unsuitable for the intended analysis. Additionally, the inaccurate solution to the velocity and pressure fields now start to affect the overall stability of the convergence in subsequent timesteps, which leads to an increase in computing time. An additional increase of the tolerance to $1e-2$ leads to reproducible convergence failures.

To save computation time – and therefore allow for a higher number of parameter studies – a solver tolerance of $1e-3$ was chosen for all model setups. Compared to the solver default values, this seems to be a relatively high number, but the consideration of strict velocity boundary conditions seem to decrease the influence of small inaccuracies of the velocity solution. Still this accuracy level is not sufficiently high to image small-scale convection features (e.g. in a rising plume) accurately. However, these kind of features are not spatially resolved by the model in 3D, so the solution is considered sufficiently good for the purpose of this thesis. For follow-up studies investigating the internal structures of plumes or unconstrained convection, a solver tolerance of at least $1e-4$ should be used.

2.2.2. Modifications of CitcomS

The modifications done to the CitcomS source code during this thesis are numerous and serve different purposes and extensions. Overall 44 main source files were modified in 293 commits, with 5374 line insertions and 723 line deletions/replacements. The source code – including a history of all changes – is available as git repository at <https://github.com/gassmoeller/citcoms/tree/rengas>, and is distributed on disc along with this thesis. The major changes introduced in CitcomS compared to the released version 3.1.1 are:

- Integration of a thermodynamical database calculated by Perple_X for ρ , α , c_p and seismic velocities after Nakagawa et al. (2010)
- Implementation of initial continents and a generation mechanism for oceanic crust and lithosphere as chemical anomalies
- Integration of a viscosity profile after Steinberger & Calderwood (2006)
- Extension of the CitcomS output routines for better support of the ParaView visualization software (binary and compressed output, more output variables, tracer

output).

- Multiple bug fixes contributed to the main development version of CitcomS

2.2.3. Extensibility and Reusability

The additions to the CitcomS codebase developed in this project were implemented with the idea of extensibility and re-usability. In particular, no existing functionality was broken or removed in this process, which was tested by regression tests of existing model cases. In these tests, a number of simple model setups were run with new revisions of the code. The new output was numerically compared to original model output to ensure their equality. This proved particularly important for the significant changes in the material model compared to the original CitcomS 3.1.1 code. The CitcomS material model is prepared to handle radially varying reference profiles for density, thermal expansivity, specific heat and gravity. However, for the purpose of the models developed for this thesis, this formalism needed to be extended to also provide a radial reference profile for the adiabatic temperature, the initial temperature, the activation energy, the radial viscosity profile, the stress exponent of the viscosity description and the thermal conductivity. In addition, the temperature and pressure dependent lookup tables of `Perple_X` needed to be included in the rest of the material model of CitcomS, without breaking the old functionality. This was achieved by utilizing function pointers in C, which are used in other parts of CitcomS already. Function pointers allow to define a pointer to a general function interface at compile time, which may then refer to different functions that implement this particular interface. Which function is called at runtime, can for example depend on user-input or configuration files. All calls to material properties in CitcomS were modularized to either use the old formalism or the new one. The whole code was separated into different files, to keep the functionality logically structured. In principle, the same formalism can be easily extended, which allows for additional material descriptions with new functionality.

2.3. Model Setup

2.3.1. Initial Conditions

Temperature

The presented model setups are generally started from one of two different initial temperature distributions. The temperature initial condition number one (TIC1) is a prescribed, only radially changing temperature profile, with boundary layers of specified age. The temperature initial condition number two (TIC2) is determined from an ongoing convection with no-slip boundary condition at the surface. Common features of both profiles are the compliance with the Boussinesq approximation, in particular the missing adiabatic temperature increase with depth. In the case of models with a chemically dense layer at the core-mantle boundary, an additional temperature jump is included, which accounts for the fact that dense material remaining at the CMB will inevitably heat up to temperatures close to the CMB temperature. The actual value of this temperature jump of 600 K was estimated from a model run that evolved until the temperature of the dense material reached a dynamic equilibrium with the cooling by subducted slabs.

Fig. 2.4 : The temperature initial conditions one and two (TIC1,TIC2) for different model setups (a) and the resulting radial viscosity profiles (b). The models started from an evolved no-slip convection (TIC2, models CMB1000L and TNCL) evolve to a higher average temperature and therefore lower viscosity compared to TIC1. Models with bottom chemical boundary layers (CMB1000, CMB1000L) start from / develop a thicker thermal boundary layer at the core-mantle boundary.

The laterally averaged initial temperatures are plotted in Figure 2.4 (a). It is noteworthy that the no-slip boundary condition for the models with TIC2 inhibits heat flux through the top surface, leading to a thick surface boundary layer and a slight increase in average lower mantle temperature of around 70 K because of radiogenic and bottom heating. Due to the strong temperature-dependency of the viscosity formulation, this leads to an average viscosity decrease of a factor of 5, as shown in Figure 2.4 (b). This needs to be taken into account when comparing the convection state of these models. For further studies other initial conditions might be worth investigating, for example the start from an ongoing convection with free-slip boundary condition, the repetition of the plate reconstruction for several times, or the use of the latest stage of the plate reconstruction for a prolonged time.

In models with prescribed chemical piles instead of a layer (see next subsection), the temperature is increased in the piles instead of the layer (TIC3, TIC4, TIC5) but otherwise identical to TIC1.

Composition

Equal to the initial condition for temperature, the initial distribution of compositional anomalies may influence the model result significantly. The initial condition of the compositional fields can be divided into models with an initial chemical anomalous layer at the core-mantle boundary and models without this layer. For most of the models an undisturbed flat, uniformly thick layer at the core-mantle boundary was used (chemical initial condition number one, CIC1). The layer is initialized with a thickness of 150 km in the reference model, equal to 2.7 vol% of the Earth's mantle. Additional models with varying thicknesses test the dependency of results on this assumption (CIC7=100 km/1.8 vol%; CIC8=60 km/1.0 vol%) For simplicity, this layer is assumed to consist of a high percentage of accumulated oceanic crust (CIC1=100%; CIC5=80%; CIC6=50%). Using the self-consistent density calculation described in Section 2.3.3, this results in a chemical density anomaly of around 2.3%/1.8%/1.2% at the core-mantle boundary.

As Torsvik et al. (2006); Burke et al. (2008); Steinberger & Torsvik (2012); Bull et al. (2014) have pointed out, the recently observed LLSVPs at the CMB may have been stable for hundreds of million of years, therefore an initial condition with prescribed piles might be more realistic than a flat layer. Since the mobility of piles on time scales longer than a few hundred million years is not constrained very well, the position of these piles is considered to be unknown. In a series of models, a distribution of the dense material with two initially prescribed piles instead of a flat layer is assumed (see Figure 2.5). The pile positions are chosen close to their present-day position (CIC2), 90 degrees rotated in longitude (CIC3) and at the rotational axis, rotated 90 degrees in latitude (CIC4). The pile geometry is defined as a cylinder in spherical coordinates, i.e. all material below a set height of 688 km above the core-mantle boundary is considered to be in the pile, if the distance along the curved surface of equal radius is smaller than a given arc length of 0.63 rad (=2488 km at the top of the pile and decreasing with radius). This creates piles with vertical sidewalls and a top boundary of constant radius. With this definition the combined volume of the two piles contains 2.7 % of Earth's mantle volume and is therefore equal to the initially flat layer setup. However, since there is no force counteracting the negative buoyancy of the piles during the initial phase of the

Fig. 2.5 : Plotted is the initial distribution of the compositionally dense material for the African hemisphere (upper panels) and the Pacific hemisphere (lower panels). The dense basal material is either initialized as uniformly thick layer (CIC1; panels **a,b**) or as separated piles at their present-day positions (CIC2; panels **c,d**; blue isosurface), 90 degrees rotated in latitude (CIC3; panels **c,d**; green isosurface) or 90 degrees rotated in longitude (CIC4; panels **c,d**; red isosurface).

model, the piles are found to broaden with time, therefore becoming more similar to CIC1, and counteracting the purpose of this model series. To lessen this problem, the basalt content of the piles is set to 80% – equal to CIC5 above. An additional model run with CIC2, but 100% basalt content, is performed to investigate the influence of this buoyancy reduction on the models.

Apart from the basal layer, all models feature the same compositional initial condition for the rest of the model domain. The mantle is assumed to consist of a mechanical mixture of 18 % basalt with 82 % harzburgite (Xu et al., 2008). The surface is divided into an oceanic and a continental part, the boundaries of the latter are defined by the reconstructed positions of continents as described in Section 2.3.2. The oceanic crust is assumed to be 7 km thick and is underlain by a 60 km thick depleted harzburgitic layer, which assumes a degree of partial melting of 11 % for mid-ocean ridge basalt. New oceanic crust and lithosphere is generated during the model run by switching the tracer material affiliation when they cross the defined depths.

For simplicity, the continents are modelled neglecting the crust, with a defined depth of the compositional boundary layer of 100 km and a density decrease of 3 % compared to background mantle material. This is highly oversimplified, but the purpose of the "continents" in these models is solely to limit the amount of entrained continental material in subducting slabs, and therefore to adjust the amount of slab material that enters the mantle to a more realistic value.

2.3.2. Boundary Conditions

Plate Reconstructions

The surface velocity of the model runs was prescribed according to a reconstruction of Phanerozoic plate motions on Earth's surface (Seton et al., 2012). The conversion from plate reconstruction to velocity boundary condition was done using the GPlates software (Boyden et al., 2011; Williams et al., 2012), which is an open-source software for interactive visualization of plate tectonics. It is developed by the EarthByte Project in the School of Geosciences at the University of Sydney, the Division of Geological and Planetary Sciences (GPS) at CalTech, and the Center for Geodynamics at the Norwegian Geological Survey (NGU). For extensive documentation and support the reader is referred to the GPlates website (<http://www.gplates.org>). The necessary algorithm to transform a geographic plate reconstruction to a global velocity boundary condition (i.e. a set of closed polygons covering the complete surface) is described by Gurnis et al. (2012). The actual dataset used for most model runs (BC1) was published by Seton et al. (2012) and provides plate motions for the past 200 Ma (plus 50 Ma of unpublished data, pers. comm. Seton et al., 2012). Their reconstruction is based on a hybrid reference frame, which merges a moving Indian/Atlantic hotspot reference frame (O'Neill et al., 2005) back to 100 Ma with a true polar wander corrected paleomagnetic reference frame (Steinberger & Torsvik, 2008) prior to this time. According to Seton et al. (2012), no information for the relative motion between the Pacific plates and Africa is available prior to 83.5 Ma, therefore the reconstruction utilizes a fixed hotspot reference frame for the Pacific hemisphere for older times (Wessel & Kroenke, 2008; Wessel et al., 2006). The approach of extending an African hotspot reference frame to the Pacific plate after 83.5 Ma without constraints from Pacific hotspot tracks introduces

some uncertainty in this approach. An update to a global hotspot reference frame like in Doubrovine et al. (2012) might provide improvements, in particular because their study showed that Pacific hotspot tracks can be matched better with a model that accounts for relative motion of the Pacific hotspots to the African reference frame. This is a possible improvement that should be investigated in further research projects.

Additionally, the plate reconstruction used in this thesis does produce periods of elevated net rotation in the lower mantle as described in Rudolph & Zhong (2014). This is an effect that is not consistent with the assumed reference frame for the plate reconstruction and therefore Rudolph & Zhong (2014) conclude: "The resolution of this disagreement between imposed and modeled net rotation for the geologic past will require a better understanding of mantle rheology, further consideration of the methods used to establish an absolute mantle reference frame, and the extent to which plume locations in the lower mantle provide an adequate proxy for an absolute mantle reference frame." Since they also point out the importance of the viscosity profile and lateral viscosity variations, a future investigation of net rotation and toroidal plate motion might be a possible follow-up project of this thesis. A discussion about net rotation and its influence on, and treatment in mantle convection models can also be found in Mihalffy et al. (2008).

Independently of these limitations, Chapter 4 discusses several changes to the used plate reconstruction by modifying the reference frame according to observed slab remnants in seismic tomography (van der Meer et al., 2009) and more regional modifications of particular subduction zones. The details of the changes are described there.

Core-Mantle Boundary Temperature

Reliable knowledge about the core-mantle boundary temperature is relatively scarce and ambiguous. While Hernlund et al. (2005) suggest temperatures between 3700 and 4400 K based on previous studies (Boehler, 2000; Alfè et al., 2002), Lay et al. (2008) assume a possible range of 3300 to 4300 K. More recent melting studies of pyrolite suggest a mantle solidus of as low as 3570 \pm 200 K (Nomura et al., 2014). Because the lowermost mantle is not molten globally, they infer this value as the maximum for the average core-mantle boundary temperature. For the purpose of this thesis, the exact value of the core-mantle boundary temperature jump is not as important as its possible influence on plume positions and the number of plumes that develop. Therefore models with three different core-mantle boundary temperature jumps from 700 to 1400 K are performed, spanning most of the previously proposed range of 500-1800 K (Lay et al., 2008).

2.3.3. Using Thermodynamic Databases for Material Properties

We used a petrological database to determine the material properties of basalt and harzburgite in the mantle (Stixrude & Lithgow-Bertelloni, 2011) following a self-consistent approach (Nakagawa et al., 2010) using previously published material compositions (Workman & Hart, 2005; Baker & Beckett, 1999). The algorithmic approach to linearize the thermodynamic equations to generate a depth-temperature equation of state for a given chemical composition is described in Connolly (2005) and implemented in the software package `Perple_X`. The program minimizes the Gibbs energy G of a system by minimizing the sum:

Table 2.1. : Bulk molar proportions of the materials for which property tables were computed.

Material	MgO	SiO ₂	FeO	CaO	Al ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	Reference
Harzburgite	56.51	36.07	6.07	0.81	0.53	0.00	Baker & Beckett (1999)
Basalt	14.94	51.75	7.06	13.88	10.19	2.18	Workman & Hart (2005)

$$G = \sum_{i=1}^{\Pi} \alpha_i G^i, \quad (2.13)$$

with Π being the number of thermodynamic phases of the system and α_i being the fraction of any particular phase i .

The composition of the general mantle was assumed to be a mechanical mixture of Basalt and Harzburgite with a basalt fraction of 18 % (Xu et al., 2008). The oxide compositions of the two materials are stated in Table 2.1 and the grid, on which their properties were computed, spans the range of 400 - 4000 K and 15 - 1325 kbar (0.015 - 132.5 GPa). There are 181 points in the temperature dimension and 262 in pressure, leading to a temperature resolution of about 20 K and a pressure resolution of 5 kbar (0.05 GPa). The pressure range was converted to a depth range by numerically integrating an adiabatic temperature/pressure profile with:

$$\frac{dT}{dp} = \frac{T\alpha(T,p)g(z)}{c_p(T,p)}, \text{ and} \quad (2.14)$$

$$\frac{dp}{dz} = \rho(T,p)g(z). \quad (2.15)$$

During the model run a bilinear interpolation was performed at each grid point and timestep to calculate the material properties at the exact temperature and pressure conditions.

Since the material database assumes a compressible material formulation, including an adiabatic temperature increase with pressure, it is necessary to adjust the "Boussinesq" model temperature to an equivalent "compressible" temperature to look up material properties. This is done via the above precalculated mantle adiabat. More specifically, the nondimensional model temperature T' is adjusted to the dimensional lookup temperature T_l by using the nondimensional surface temperature T'_0 , the dimensional adiabatic temperatures $T_a(z)$ at the depth z , and $T_a(z=0)$ at the depth 0, and the temperature scaling ΔT as follows:

$$T_l = \Delta T(T' + T'_0) + (T_a(z) - T_a(z=0)) \quad (2.16)$$

Furthermore, the use of the Boussinesq approximation combined with the self-consist-

Fig. 2.6 : Test cases to ensure the correct derivation and implementation of the new material model. Shown is the temperature deviation from the reference temperature / temperature profile. The comparison between the usual Boussinesq (a) / Truncated anelastic liquid (b) density calculation and the new scaled lookup tables approach (c,d) reveals only slightest differences after a model runtime of 100 Ma.

ent approach described above makes it necessary to scale the resulting buoyancy with a laterally averaged density profile to correct for compressible effects not consistent with the incompressibility assumption of the equations. This can be illustrated by considering the depth-dependency of ρ in the buoyancy calculation. The usual notation of the Boussinesq approximation

$$\delta\rho = \rho_0\alpha_0\Delta T, \quad (2.17)$$

changes in the compressible case to:

$$\delta\rho(z) = \bar{\rho}_0(z)\alpha_0\Delta T. \quad (2.18)$$

Because the `Perple_X` approach described above always calculates $\delta\rho$ after Equation 2.18, and in the nondimensional formulation $\rho_0 = 1$, the scaled buoyancy in the Boussinesq approximation case can be defined as:

$$\delta\rho = \frac{\delta\rho(z)}{\bar{\rho}_0(z)}, \quad (2.19)$$

with $\bar{\rho}_0(z)$ – the reference density in dependence of depth – being easily determinable in the usual anelastic liquid approximation, e.g. the analytic solution of the used equation of state. In the lookup table approach however, it needs to be determined as the density at the adiabatic temperature in that depth (see Equation 2.14).

To illustrate and benchmark the equality between the two approaches, simplified 2D models were created using the software `ASPECT`. These four models assume the usual thermal buoyancy calculation in the Boussinesq (Equation 2.17) and truncated anelastic liquid (Equation 2.18) approximation on the one hand, and the adjusted (Equation 2.19) or not adjusted lookup density calculation on the other hand. All models share otherwise identical boundary and initial conditions except for the conditions affected by the changing compressibility approximations. The model setup comprises a quarter of a 2D shell with free-slip boundary conditions on three boundaries and a no-slip boundary condition at the surface. The temperature is fixed at 273 K at the top and at 2600 / 4250 K at the bottom in the incompressible / compressible case respectively. With the chosen material properties the difference of 1650 K matches exactly the radial adiabatic temperature increase over the model domain. The initial temperature field is perturbed by a sinusoidal perturbation of magnitude 200 K and wavelength of 2/3 of the horizontal model extent, leading to two initial upwellings and one downwelling with zero perturbation at the boundaries.

The material data table for the two lookup table models was calculated with the anelastic liquid approximation for density anomalies, therefore the resulting convection in models two and four (anelastic liquid approximation) should match exactly if the lookup table approach is implemented correctly. Additionally, the convection in models one and three (Boussinesq approximation) should develop identically, if Equation 2.19 is derived and implemented in the right way.

The results after 100 Ma – or more than one overturn time in these simplified models

– are shown in Figure 2.6. The nearly identical temperature fields of panels (b) and (d) ensures the correct implementation of the lookup-table algorithm for the anelastic liquid approximation. Moreover, the equality of panels (a) and (c) suggests the correctness of the approach of scaling a compressible data table to the incompressible Boussinesq approximation case as described in Equation 2.19. The remaining differences can be attributed to at least two reasons. First, the necessary interpolation in the lookup table approach will introduce slight numerical deviations, which add up over model run time. Second, the necessary numerical integration of Equations 2.14 and 2.15 will also provide a source of round-off errors, which might change the reference density calculation of Equation 2.19. Therefore, a full equality of the two approaches can not be achieved.

Despite the small differences, the lookup table approach will be used for the models of this thesis because of its more realistic material description. A model with simplified analytic density calculation will test the dependency of the model results on the material description.

2.3.4. Viscosity Description

The deformation mechanisms of mantle material – in particular in the lower mantle – are still very poorly constrained. Although after Schubert et al. (2001) the idea of a mantle that adjusts like a fluid was accepted since the end of the 19th century, the observations to investigate it are strongly limited. This is mainly caused by the vastly different time-scale viscous deformation of the Earth occurs on. Observations that provide possible constraints are generally divided into reactions of the Earth to changing loads, and laboratory measurements about the properties of mantle materials. Both include a number of difficulties. While observations about the Earth’s reactions feature similar spatial and time scales as mantle convection, they are intimately linked to unknowns like the lithospheric structure of the area of investigation. Laboratory experiments allow for very controlled experimental conditions and might be able to also investigate non-linear viscous behaviour; however, they lack the possibility to investigate on the same spatial and time scales as mantle convection. Therefore the scaling to realistic conditions adds an additional uncertainty.

In this work two different viscosity descriptions are investigated, which are recently published and widely used (see Figure 2.7). The first one is a work by Steinberger & Calderwood (2006) and considers the Haskell constraint on geoid, radial heat-flow modelling, melting curves and others. It assumes the common definition of viscosity as

$$\eta = \dot{\epsilon}^{\frac{1}{n}-1} * \frac{1}{2C_1^{\frac{1}{n}}} \exp\left(\frac{H}{nRT}\right), \quad (2.20)$$

which is simplified in the presented models by neglecting dislocation creep ($n = 1$) to:

$$\eta = C e^{\frac{H}{RT}}. \quad (2.21)$$

Analogous to the approach of Steinberger & Calderwood (2006), the temperature is split into a radially averaged reference profile and a lateral temperature perturbation by considering:

Fig. 2.7 : Comparison between the viscosity descriptions of Steinberger & Calderwood (2006, red) and Bower et al. (2013, black). The plot reveals large differences in both temperature- (a) and depth-dependency (b). While the description of Bower et al. (2013) does not need a cut-off value due to its reduced temperature-dependency, the steeper gradients of the description by Steinberger & Calderwood (2006) take into account thermodynamic expectations.

$$\frac{1}{T} = \frac{1}{\bar{T}} - \frac{\delta T}{\bar{T}(\bar{T} + \delta T)}. \quad (2.22)$$

This allows us to consider the viscosity as

$$\eta = \eta_i * V_{rT}(z) * V_{IT}, \quad (2.23)$$

with

$$V_{IT}(\delta T) = e^{-\frac{H\delta T}{RT(\bar{T} + \delta T)}}, \quad (2.24)$$

and

$$v_{rT}(z) = e^{\frac{H(z)}{RT(z)}}. \quad (2.25)$$

The other approach, used for example by McNamara & Zhong (2005); Zhong et al. (2008); Gurnis et al. (2012); Bower et al. (2013), accounts individually for the expected viscosity jump at Earth's internal boundary layers and uses a simplified approach for the temperature-dependency, which is justified by the large uncertainties. It uses a radial profile, with a reference lithosphere viscosity of $\eta_0 = 5 \cdot 10^{21}$ Pas and a viscosity decrease to $1/30 \cdot \eta_0$ in the upper mantle. The lower mantle viscosity increases linearly from $2.0 \cdot \eta_0$ to $6.8 \cdot \eta_0$ with depth. This radial profile is superimposed on a temperature dependency following:

$$\eta(z, T) = \eta(z) * \exp(A(T - 0.5)), \quad (2.26)$$

with A being the dimensionless activation energy and chosen to be 9.21, which corresponds to 172 kJ/mol, resulting in a temperature variation of four orders of magnitude over the model temperature range:

$$\eta_{T'=0} = 10^4 \cdot \eta_{T'=1}. \quad (2.27)$$

Both viscosity profiles feature a viscosity range of about $10^{20} - 10^{23}$ Pas with a low viscosity asthenospheric layer (around 10^{20} Pas), a viscosity jump of around 2 orders of magnitude at the spinel-perovskite phase transition (~ 660 km depth), and an increase of viscosity in the lower mantle. Steinberger & Calderwood (2006) generally incorporate up to factor 2 higher reference viscosities, but also include a much stronger temperature-dependency (Figure 2.7) and therefore in general feature much larger viscosity contrasts.

Since in both profiles the depth-dependence is quite easily separable from the temperature-dependence, a third model was tested in which the depth-dependence of Steinberger & Calderwood (2006) was combined with the temperature-dependence of Bower et al. (2013). This combination isolates the effect of the different descriptions for the temperature-dependence.

Table 2.2. : Reference model parameters. Note that these are reference values, many values can vary locally in dependence of depth or temperature.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Rayleigh number	$8.347e + 08$	—
Initial temperature	1613	K
Radiogenic heating rate	$6 * 10^{-12}$	$\frac{W}{kg}$
Earth's radius	$6.371 * 10^6$	m
Model depth	$2.867 * 10^6$	m
Density	3340	$\frac{kg}{m^3}$
Thermal diffusivity	$1 * 10^{-6}$	$\frac{m^2}{s}$
Gravitational acceleration	9.81	$\frac{m}{s^2}$
Thermal expansivity	$4.21 * 10^{-5}$	$\frac{1}{K}$
Reference viscosity	10^{21}	$Pa \cdot s$
Specific heat	1200	$\frac{J}{kgK}$

2.3.5. List of Models

The final set of calculated and interpreted model setups is listed in Table 2.3 and 2.4. All models share some common reference values, while others are modified as listed in the tables. The constant scaling values for the reference model setup are given in Table 2.2. A short summary of the most important results for every model setup is listed in Appendix B.

Table 2.3. : List of model setups for investigating the influence of plate motions and model assumptions on the generation of plumes. Abbreviations are explained in the previous sections, and results and interpretations are given in Chapter 3. SC2006 stands for viscosity profile of Steinberger & Calderwood (2006) and NZ for viscosity profile of McNamara & Zhong (2005).

Name	ΔT CMB	Chemical Anomaly	Velocity BC	Temp. IC	Comp. IC	Material	Viscosity
CMB1000	1000	Layer	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC1	CIC1	Perple_X	SC2006
CMB700	700	Layer	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC1	CIC1	Perple_X	SC2006
CMB1400	1400	Layer	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC1	CIC1	Perple_X	SC2006
TNP	1000	Layer	free-slip	TIC1	CIC1	Perple_X	SC2006
TNC	1000	-	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC1	-	Perple_X	SC2006
TS	1000	Layer	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC1	CIC1	SIMPLE	SC2006
TV	1000	Layer	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC1	CIC1	Perple_X	NZ2005
TV2	1000	Layer	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC1	CIC1	Perple_X	Combined
CMB1000L	1000	Layer	Seton et al. (2012) after no-slip	TIC2	CIC1	Perple_X	SC2006
TNCL	1000	-	Seton et al. (2012) after no-slip	TIC2	-	Perple_X	SC2006
CIC2	1000	2 domes current pos	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC3	CIC2	Perple_X	SC2006
CIC3	1000	2 domes polar	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC4	CIC3	Perple_X	SC2006
CIC4	1000	2 domes rotated	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC5	CIC4	Perple_X	SC2006
CIC2-100	1000	2 domes current	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC1	CIC2	Perple_X	SC2006
CMB1000-50	1000	50% Layer	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC1	CIC5	Perple_X	SC2006
CMB1000-80	1000	80% Layer	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC1	CIC6	Perple_X	SC2006
CMB1000-1.8%	1000	100 km Layer	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC1	CIC7	Perple_X	SC2006
CMB1000-1.0%	1000	60 km Layer	Seton et al. (2012)	TIC1	CIC8	Perple_X	SC2006

Table 2.4. : List of model setups for investigating the influence of plate reconstruction changes on plume generation. Results and interpretations are given in Chapter 4. PS stands for Phoenix-subduction zone

Name	Number	Reference frame	PS Position	PS Direction	PS Speed
CMB1000	1	Seton et al. (2012)	unchanged	unchanged	unchanged
Close	2	Seton et al. (2012)	Close	unchanged	unchanged
Far	3	rotated van der Meer et al. (2009)	Far	unchanged	unchanged
Both	4	rotated van der Meer et al. (2009)	Close	unchanged	unchanged
Slow	5	rotated van der Meer et al. (2009)	Close	unchanged	Slow
Fast	6	rotated van der Meer et al. (2009)	Close	unchanged	Fast
30 deg	7	rotated van der Meer et al. (2009)	Close	30 deg	unchanged
60 deg	8	rotated van der Meer et al. (2009)	Close	60 deg	unchanged

Fig. 2.8 : Overview over created model setups. The interpreted models for Chapter 3 and 4 are marked in separate boxes. Connections mark groups of models, which are used to discuss specific questions, such as the dependence on initial conditions.

2.4. Interpreting Model Results

2.4.1. Spatial Point Set Distributions

In this thesis, the generated plume positions will be used as a measure for the similarity between model results and surface observations. Therefore, some different methods to compare a set of points to another point set will be described in this and the following section.

In general, the comparison of point set data in terms of measuring the similarity of their positions poses some challenges to the metric used. One can either compare the datasets by calculating characteristic properties and comparing those (as is done in Subsection 2.4.2) or by defining a metric between individual points and calculating the statistical probability to achieve such a fit. The latter approach will be described in this section.

If considering two given point sets A and B – with a number of N_A points in A and N_B points in B – then a similarity test between the two distributions may be defined as follows: Computing the minimum distance between the individual points of A and B and comparing the proportion of points X closer than a certain threshold r to the proportion p_r of a large random point distribution and the given dataset A or B . If X is significantly larger than p_r then the match of the two point data sets is significantly better than a random fit. Here, a deviation of two standard deviations from the expected value of p_r is considered significant. The standard deviation used for minimal distances of point distributions on a sphere is calculated as (Trauth et al., 2007):

$$\sigma = \sqrt{N_A * p_r * (1 - p_r)} / N_A. \quad (2.28)$$

A different way of plotting this significance is to consider the probability of a statistical experiment to reach a fit of this quality. This can be described by the probability of a Binomial distribution:

$$P(a) = \sum_{x=a}^{N_A} \binom{N_A}{x} p^x (1-p)^{N_A-x}, \quad (2.29)$$

where a is the number of successful tries in the model, i.e. the number of points that are closer than the chosen distance r to the reference point set and N_A is the number of tries, i.e. points. The probability p to be closer than the chosen distance to the reference point set is hereby approximated by the proportion p_r mentioned above. This is possible, because the average of a random dataset approaches the statistically expected value if the dataset is sufficiently large. With this formulation the probability can be plotted in dependency of the area fraction of Earth's surface that is covered by circles of the chosen distance r around present-day hotspots. Graphically this can be illustrated as shown in Figure 2.9.

Of course the probability could also be plotted over the chosen distance r itself, which is equivalent to a (nonlinear) scaling of the x-axis of the plot. This approach is demonstrated in Figure B.3. Because the linear dependency of the fraction of model plumes and area fraction of Earth that is covered provides a simpler comparison, the former approach will be used, but the latter one is equally valid.

In the performed analysis the distinction between reference distribution and test dis-

Fig. 2.9 : (a): Comparison of a plume point data set A (blue triangles) to a set of hotspot positions B. Surface area close to hotspot positions B is coloured in orange. (b): Example distributions compared to average distribution (orange line). The investigated point distributions are either very similar to the reference (blue line), completely random (light blue line) or very regularly distributed across Earth's surface (yellow). The blue and yellow lines are actual convection model results described later in more detail. (c): Probability distributions for this example datasets calculated after Equation 2.29. The borders of the band plot are the two possible approaches to define point data and reference data (see description in Subsection 2.4.1).

tribution is not completely clear. At first, one would want to use the observed hotspot positions at the surface as reference dataset, and compare the model plumes to this distribution. However, since the hotspots in the catalogue might be created by more than one source mechanism (e.g. small-scale convection in the upper mantle as in Ballmer et al., 2007), the opposite analysis of using the model plumes as reference and comparing the observed hotspots to this reference distribution is reasonable as well. Since it is not clear which analysis is preferable in this work, both will be presented in the form of a band plot (see Figure 2.9 c). The width of the resulting band will give the difference between the two methods. Later on it is shown that the choice of which analysis to prefer does not influence the main points of this thesis, but shows some minor differences.

Another important choice for this analysis is the set of compared hotspot catalogues. We will discuss this choice in Subsection 2.4.3 and the chosen catalogue is listed in Table A.1. The differences between the hotspot catalogues are not significant to the main results presented.

2.4.2. Spatial Clustering

A second approach to comparing two point data sets is to compare their characteristics. One of these characteristics is the amount and position of clustering that is occurring within the dataset. The cluster analysis in this thesis was performed with the algorithms KMeans (Lloyd, 1982) as implemented in the SciPy package (Jones et al., 2001) and DBSCAN (Ester et al., 1996) as implemented in the SKLearn package (Pedregosa et al., 2011). KMeans is a widely used spatial analysis tool, in which the set of data points is attributed to a manually prescribed number of clusters, and the sums of the distances between data points and their corresponding cluster centres are calculated (see Figure 2.11 for an example). In the course of the algorithm, both the attribution of the points, and the position of the cluster centres are iteratively changed to minimize this sum. In general, the analysis is dependent on the choice of the initial cluster centres, because it falls into local minima of the distribution. Therefore, for all subsequently presented cluster distributions 20 repeated computations with random initial cluster centres were performed, and the minimum distortion of all model runs was used for further analysis. It is noteworthy, that the small overall number of plumes of around 20 to 40 in these models poses a challenge to this kind of cluster analysis, because a small change in the number of the plumes may lead to a jump in the attribution of plumes to the clusters. In the presented models, however, this behaviour is not observed for different plume sets, which were selected with varying plume excess temperatures.

KMeans was chosen for its simplicity and stable behaviour; however, it suffers a drawback, which is the predetermined number of clusters the dataset is separated into. Because many studies argue to separate hotspots on Earth into two hemispherical groups, it seems reasonable to prescribe a number of two clusters. Nevertheless, it is not certain that this proves to be the optimal number of clusters. A determination of a suitable number of clusters for KMeans is usually done by plotting the amount of cluster distortion over the number of clusters as shown in panel a of Figure 2.10. Cluster distortion is defined as the remaining average distance between the model points and their affiliated cluster center. In strongly clustered datasets this curve features an observable kink at the optimal number of clusters, when all reasonably clustered points are very close to cluster centres and only statistical noise lies outside of the clusters. The clustering of the

Fig. 2.10 : (a) The KMeans cluster distortion defined as the average distance between observations and associated cluster centres is plotted over the number of clusters generated for the observed hotspots and two exemplary models. (b) The number of generated clusters with the DBSCAN algorithm in dependence of its input parameters ϵ (Maximal distance in Earth's radii) and N_p (Minimal samples within this distance) for the observed hotspot distribution on Earth. (c) Like (b) but for the reference model CMB1000 with plate motions. (d) Like (b), but for the model TNP without prescribed plate motions.

observed hotspots however, is more focussed at the boundaries of the LLSVPs instead of their centres (Torsvik et al., 2006), therefore this kink at optimal cluster number is not apparent in our datasets. Thus, a different cluster algorithm – DBSCAN (Ester et al., 1996) – was used to compute the optimal number of cluster centres. DBSCAN is capable of determining the optimal number of clusters in dependence of the two model parameters ϵ and N_p . For this purpose it identifies a number of core samples in the dataset, which are defined as having more than N_p neighbour samples within a distance of ϵ , i.e. are in a very populated area of the model domain. All core samples that are separated closer than ϵ are attributed to one cluster, while all samples that are not core samples are assigned the nearest cluster, without becoming core samples. This way the algorithm does not only automatically determine the number of clusters, but it is also capable of forming concave or more complex cluster shapes (think for example of two rings of datapoints around a common center). This algorithm is of course prone to a mutual selection of input parameters to create the number of clusters one expects. Therefore, Figure 2.10 **b-d** displays the determined number of clusters for different point datasets in dependence of the parameters within reasonable ranges. Some features in these plots are common to all datasets – namely the increase in the optimal cluster number for low N_p and small ϵ . In this case many small clusters of only a few points are formed. For very low ϵ and increasing N_p no cluster is formed, because there is not one region in the pointset that shows a very strong clustering of many points within shortest distances. Additionally, for very large ϵ all points are merged into one global cluster that covers the whole surface. Reassuringly though, for the observed hotspot positions (**b**) and the models with plate motions (**c**), a reasonably large region in these plots suggest a separation into two clusters. It is particularly interesting that this region does not exist in a random dataset of points (**d**), therefore suggesting that a separation of the datasets into two cluster is a reasonable assumption. Based on this investigation, the later on presented observations and models will utilize the KMeans algorithm with two clusters.

2.4.3. Hotspot Catalogue

Over the years, a large number of hotspot catalogues and estimates for the related plume buoyancy flux and other hotspot properties were created, e.g. Davies (1988); Sleep (1990); Steinberger (2000a). For the purpose of defining a hotspot, different observables have been discussed (Courtillot et al., 2003). In fact, one of the main observations for the existence of mantle plumes from the beginning on was the observation of "swells" in ocean bathymetry and continental topography close to intra-plate volcanism (Wilson, 1963; Morgan, 1971). However, as King & Adam (2014) showed in a new compilation for swell buoyancy flux, the choice of calculation method for buoyancy flux and swell topography is far from unique. In fact they state: "The differences between the results we calculate using different methods does not reflect a limitation in the data and has much more to do with subjective choices by the researcher". Following their results the prominent swells around the largest hotspots are likely only explainable by plume heatflux from the core-mantle boundary, although a calculation of hotspot buoyancy flux and therefore core-mantle boundary heat flux is subject to an uncertainty of around 40 % for large hotspots and 50–80 % for smaller ones. Since similar limitations apply to all other hotspot definition criteria (see reviews by White (2010); Ito & van Keken (2007)), there is still argument about the exact number and definition of hotspots.

Fig. 2.11 : The used hotspot catalogue (triangles) is plotted on top of global coastlines and altitude. The hotspots are separated into two clusters by the KMeans algorithm described in Section 2.4.2 and colored white/black according to their cluster affiliation. The cluster centers are represented by gray diamonds.

For this thesis, the hotspot catalogue of Steinberger (2000a) was used and updated with observations of recent years. The updates mostly influence the exact position and number of plumes in the South Atlantic (O'Connor et al., 2012) and add the Hainan plume at the Southern Chinese coast (Lei et al., 2009). The catalogue is not thought to be exclusive and neither does it assume to include only deep mantle plumes. However, since only the statistical distribution and properties are compared, its accuracy and comprehensive listing of intraplate volcanism provides the characteristics that can be compared against model results. An exact listing of the used hotspot positions is given in Section A.1 and the global distribution of these hotspots is plotted in Figure 2.11.

Still there is an important decision to be made about which of the hotspots should be included for the analysis. Simply incorporating all hotspots in the catalogue is the choice least likely influenced by choosing bias and thus would be preferable. However, the used catalogue comprises a lot of small anomalies that might be caused by local features rather than mantle plumes. In particular, in convection models that only produce a small number of plumes it could be preferable to compare the set of model plumes to the most probable plume positions on Earth instead of all catalogue entries, which is for example done in Steinberger & Torsvik (2012). Due to the large number of plumes generated in most of the presented models (≥ 20 plumes), all hotspots of the catalogue (45 hotspots) will be used for comparison in this thesis.

2.4.4. Seismic Tomography

A number of studies have discussed the comparison of convection models to seismic observations and many are mentioned in Subsection 1.5 and 1.3. In this subsection the potential consequences and limitations of comparisons between seismic tomography and mantle convection models will be summarized. The challenges in these comparisons arise from two major uncertainties.

The first is a limitation of the mantle convection model to the solution variables pressure, velocity, temperature and compositional variation. For the comparison to seismic observations, obviously a conversion of these variables to seismic velocities is necessary. This conversion, however, is far from well constrained. While seismic velocities of minerals or mineral assemblages can be measured on a laboratory scale, they are also sensitive to factors not well constrained in most convection models, like the amount of available volatile elements and fluids like partial melt. Additionally, the dependency of seismic velocities on temperature and pressure can change at phase transitions, adding another element of complexity. In practice, this conversion is generally calculated by assuming a constant- or depth-dependent conversion factor between temperature and seismic velocity and where necessary adding a compositional contribution. The self-consistent approach described in Subsection 2.3.3 incorporates these complexities and allows for a numerically self-consistent conversion for the given compositions at thermodynamic equilibrium. Nonetheless, it still neglects volatiles that might change the calculation and the remaining uncertainty about mantle major element compositions and distributions. Despite these shortcomings, the same approach was also employed in previous works like Nakagawa et al. (2010); Xu et al. (2008); Schuberth (2009).

The second uncertainty is related to the way seismic tomography models are constructed. Since the creation of a tomography model is a complex inverse process, trying to match the existing observations with the known earthquake source parameters via

a seismic velocity distribution, it requires assumptions and simplifications to be stable and produce reasonable results. One of the assumptions is the weighting towards a minimized velocity anomaly that is assumed to filter noise and statistical outliers. While this approach is necessary for the creation and stabilization of the model, it will inevitably result in models with the smallest necessary amount of seismic velocity deviation, which might be smaller than the actual deviation. This behaviour can be improved by enhanced data quality and a better ray coverage, because then less damping is required to find stable solutions. A second limitation is also connected to the available ray coverage, namely the spatial resolution of the resulting model. For a high reliability of the model, a large number of crossing ray paths for every model cell is favourable. However, to reach higher numbers of source-receiver combinations per cell, the spatial resolution needs to be decreased. In particular, due to the uneven distribution of sources (mostly at active plate margins) and receivers (mostly in the northern hemisphere), the reliability of a tomography model might be highly uneven. Models with variable spatial resolution like Savani (Auer et al., 2014) or P07 (Amaru, 2007), which will be used in this thesis, can lessen this limitation, but still suffer from the mentioned uneven ray coverage. In fact, Boschi et al. (2007) argue that the available source-receiver combinations are the largest limitation to current-day tomography models. Finally, all tomography models are limited by their assumed model for wave / ray propagation. Since the inversion of a global full-waveform tomography model is still nearly impossible due to computational limitations, all available tomographies employ different simplifications, like the pre-computation of sensitivity kernels (regions that are "sampled" by a given source-receiver combination), the assumption of constant sensitivity kernels or varying types of ray approximations. While most of these approximations are valid up to certain points, it is important to remember their limitations. These are, for example, the effect of wavefront-healing that hides low-velocity anomalies (Nolet & Dahlen, 2000), the smearing of interfaces that are detectable by direct seismic observations and the averaging of small-scale heterogeneities into smooth features. Some of these limitations can be quantified and applied to the convection model as well in the form of the seismic resolution operator as described in (Schuberth et al., 2009a; Bull et al., 2009). However, this approach only accounts for the known resolution effects, and does neglect the assumptions made concerning the wave propagation. Additionally, it introduces the problem of energy loss due to conversion between different parametrizations of models that needs to be corrected for (Schuberth et al., 2009a).

Despite all of the above mentioned uncertainties, the comparison between convection models is still one of the most valuable observation to compare with convection models. Therefore, the comparisons in this thesis will be done with these limitations in mind. For future studies, a default publication of the necessary data to apply the above mentioned resolution filtering would help establishing a standardized procedure for comparisons between convection models and tomography models.

3. The Influence of Global Plate Movements on Mantle Plumes

3.1. Resulting Plume Distribution

3.1.1. Time Evolution of Reference Model

The reference model CMB1000 starts from an undisturbed initial condition as described in Subsection 2.3.1. When the plate movements at the surface start to create subduction zones at 250 Ma, it takes until 210 Ma for the slabs to develop, reach the lower mantle and have a significant influence on the lowermost mantle structure (shown in Figure 3.1). It is important to note that the slabs themselves do not reach the core-mantle boundary until 150 Ma (100 Ma after their start). Their influence on the lower-mantle velocity field, however, is already shaping the thermo-chemical boundary layer into two loosely disconnected piles at 200 Ma. At 150–100 Ma the first plumes begin to develop, the first one being in the Eastern Pacific hemisphere, until at 100 Ma already 9 plumes have reached the surface at locations close to the CAMP, Iceland and Kerguelen locations in the African hemisphere and relatively distributed across the Pacific. The plumes in this stage develop at the edges of the thermo-chemical piles as boundary-layer instabilities pushed by the interplay between the flow fields of the subducting slab and the resistance of the dense material. All of the developed plumes up to this point, are long-lived features until present-day state, although some of them split up into several smaller plumes in the course of convection. Note that around this timespan of slightly more than 100 Ma of plate reconstructions was available for the study of McNamara & Zhong (2005), and although the time ranges differ (120 Ma to today vs. 250 Ma to 100 Ma), the general interpretation that it needs at least 100–150 Ma to coarsely resemble Earth-like geometries in a convection model remains valid.

While most of the African plumes at this time are relatively stable with movements of around thousand kilometres per hundred million years ($\approx 1 \frac{cm}{y}$), around half of the Pacific plumes move around significantly in the early stage of their life (up to 5000 km per hundred million years, $\approx 5 \frac{cm}{y}$). However, this seems to be an effect of the model setup and the still ongoing development of a realistic convection pattern, because during the last 50 million years of the model runtime the plume positions seem to stabilize, with movements being on the order of at most $1 \frac{cm}{y}$. This interpretation is supported by the fact that the initial fast motion of some Pacific plumes seems to be caused by two main reasons. The first one is the shift of the edges of the thermo-chemical piles, to which the plumes seem to be strongly connected. This shift is happening relatively slowly and is similar in the African and Pacific hemisphere. The second reason is the movement of the plumes to more favourable positions along the edge of the piles. While all plumes seem to form more easily at the edges, straight edges seem to be less likely to form plumes than bent or kinked edges. Therefore, if a plume forms at a straight edge it usually migrates

Fig. 3.1 : Shown is the time evolution of the African hemisphere (top rows) and Pacific hemisphere (bottom rows) of the reference model. The isosurface represents temperatures 250 K hotter than average mantle. The colours represent height above the core-mantle boundary and coastlines are plotted for spatial orientation. Green spheres are plotted at current-day hotspot positions and blue spheres represent current-day plume positions in the model.

in the next tens of millions of years to more favourable positions. Because the Pacific pile has a rounder shape – compared to the prolonged one of the African pile – a number of plumes form at relatively smooth edges and migrate with relatively high speed to a distant kink afterwards. Whether this behaviour can be observed on Earth would need to be investigated in a follow-up study to this thesis, although this observations suggest to refine the idea of plume generation zones to sharply bent margins of thermo-chemical piles. In general, this lateral movement of the plume origin also allows plumes to merge, although it can not be observed in the reference model.

The further evolution is governed by a stabilization of the convection pattern. The number of plumes increases due to the growth of new plumes and partition of old plumes, while the average size and excess temperatures of plumes decrease. Some of the now smaller plumes also cease to exist or degenerate into a less pronounced upwelling of negligible excess temperature. The process of partitioning of plumes is for example observable in the south-east corner of Figure 3.1 on the African hemisphere between 100 Ma and 0 Ma. A strong plume arrives at the surface, but with the overall westward motion of the southern pile boundary and the generation of the East-African rift plume to the north two strong forces exist that drag the plume material into opposing directions. The plume therefore evolves into a wide upwelling without clear plume head at 50 Ma and finally splits up into two completely separated plumes at present day, one close to the position of Reunion and another close to Kerguelen. In fact, 30 Ma after the present-day state (run with constant plate motions of today) the plume close to Reunion vanishes and joins the upwelling beneath East Africa (see Figure B.1).

3.1.2. Model Plume Distribution and Earth's Hotspot Distribution

In this subsection the plume positions and distribution in the set of reference models are discussed and compared to the observed hotspot positions on Earth. The comparison uses the methods described in Subsection 2.4.1. As shown in Figure 3.2 **a**, the fraction of model plumes that lie within a certain distance of the nearest present-day hotspot is plotted and compared to the part of the Earth's surface that is covered by circles of this radius around the hotspots. In a random distribution of plumes (i.e. each plume has the same probability to reach the surface at every point) these numbers should be coincident within the random deviations indicated by the 2-standard-deviation (σ) error bars. This is precisely the case for the test model without plate reconstruction (yellow line in Figure 3.2). The reference model, however, shows a much higher amount of mantle plumes close to modern hotspots (blue line). The fraction of plumes close to hotspots is always larger than the area fraction that is covered, and for a range of distances between 500 and 1500 km it is about twice as high. From 1500 km distance on there is a saturation effect in this plot, since nearly all plumes are contained in the circles and also the amount of Earth's surface that is covered by circles is larger than 50 %. Following a binomial distribution the probability to achieve our – or a better – result by a random process is partly lower than 1 % (Figure 3.2 **b**), which is equivalent to a nearly 3-sigma deviation in a normal distribution (dark gray area). Usually a 2-sigma deviation of a statistical measurement (orange error bars in Figure 3.2 **a** and light gray area in Figure 3.2 **b**) is considered significant; therefore for most of the distance range the fit of our model is highly significant. Especially the range from 1000 to 1500 km distance shows remarkably low probabilities, although the whole range from 750 to 2250

Fig. 3.2 : (a) The fraction of plumes in the reference model that lie within a given distance around the nearest surface hotspot (blue) always exceeds the area fraction that these circles cover of Earth’s surface (orange). A model without a prescribed surface motion is plotted for comparison (yellow). Error bars show the 2-sigma confidence intervals around the random distribution. The error bars are dependent on the number of model plumes, which differs slightly between models. For comparability all error bars in subsequent plots are calculated and shown for the reference model. (b) The probability of a binomial distribution to create the observed fit or a better one is plotted, assuming the amount of Earth covered (orange line in a) as the probability for a single plume to reach the surface close to a hotspot. The light and dark gray areas show the 4.45 % and 0.3 % value, corresponding to a 2-sigma and 3-sigma deviation in a normal distribution, respectively. The band plot of possibilities results out of two different approaches to calculate the probabilities as described in Subsection 2.4.1.

Fig. 3.3 : Statistics of the observed fit between model plumes and Earth’s hotspots. In addition to Figure 3.2, test models that start from an ongoing convection (green, model CMB1000L) and a purely thermal convection model (light blue, model TNC) are shown. Additionally, in this plot the original hotspot database from Steinberger (2000a) is used. The differences to the modified hotspot database in Figure 3.2 are only visible by careful comparison. The error bars are calculated according to the plume number of the green model; the bars for the blue models are slightly larger and nearly identical to the ones from Figure 3.2. (b) The probabilities for both additional models reach similar significance levels as the reference model CMB1000, but only for larger plume-hotspot distances. This suggests the reference model is particularly good at fitting hotspot positions for very close matches.

km reaches sufficient values.

The remaining deviation between reference model plumes and observed hotspots may be related to a number of possible reasons. First of all, the model parameters still have major uncertainties, for example in the viscosity description and the not completely understood major element composition and distribution of material in the Earth’s mantle, as well as the unknown initial state of convection. But additionally, accumulating evidence has arisen for possible displacement of up to a few hundred kilometres between plume impingement position and hotspot volcanism (Ballmer et al., 2013; Rychert et al., 2013). This deviation limits the precision of any mantle convection model to this accuracy, as long as it does not account for melt-lithosphere-crust interaction.

Test models – one without a chemical layer (TNC) and one starting from an already existing convection (CMB1000L) – reach less but still significant agreement in large parts of the distance range (see Figure 3.3). The model without prescribed plate velocities (TNP), however, remains far above the 2-sigma probability line for all distances, and

is therefore considered as being not related to the existing hotspot distribution. The probabilities and Earth's surface coverage for all models in this plot were calculated using the original unmodified hotspots database after Steinberger (2000a). Therefore, the very subtle difference of the blue and yellow line to the distribution of Figure 3.2 is suggesting that the extension of the hotspot catalogue did not influence our result. The very precise match between test model TNP (yellow line) and area fraction (orange line) in Figures 3.2 and 3.3 most probably stems from the plume dynamics in an undisturbed convection model. The spacing between neighboring plumes in the test model is closer to equidistant than expected for a random distribution of independent plumes, because close plumes merge, and the remaining ones are mostly centered in convection cells. As described in Subsection 2.4.1, for such nearly equidistant spacing plume fraction closely follows area fraction. Therefore, the deviation of the presented reference model (blue line) from the area fraction (orange line) is even more significant than the formal error bars suggest.

3.1.3. Plume and Hotspot Clustering

An interpretation of the resulting plume distribution into two separate clusters following the methods of Subsection 2.4.2 leads to the results presented in Figure 3.4. The two upper panels in Figure 3.4 display the observed hotspot distribution and reference model plume distribution, respectively. The two recognized clusters are located very similarly and the distance between the cluster centers is as low as 910 km for the African cluster and 2144 km for the Pacific cluster. The boundary between the two clusters follows in both cases the West-American subduction zones, the Kuril trench and Japan trench to the South-West, crossing Antarctica to a closing circle. Regions of hotspots that are not reproduced by the convection model are the North-African hotspots like Hoggar and Tibesti, and the West-American hotspots like Yellowstone, Bowie and Cobb. An additional hotspot in most convection models forms at the north-eastern ending of the African cluster in North-western Russia.

3.2. Model Parameter Sensitivity

3.2.1. Core-Mantle Boundary Temperature Jump

The variation of the core-mantle boundary temperature and hence the Rayleigh number from a temperature jump of 700 K to 1400 K displays no dramatic change in large-scale convection pattern as shown in Figure 3.5. The same two piles are created since the subducting slabs are relatively unaffected. The shape of the piles however is changed in detail. The CMB700 model develops slightly more broadened piles, while the topography of the piles in the CMB1400 model significantly increases, leading to less CMB area covered by the piles. In particular, the Pacific pile in the CMB1400 model degenerates into a ring-like ridge around a central 'hole'. This suggests an entrainment and destruction of the chemical layer over time. Additionally, the number and individual position of plumes is significantly affected by the temperature change. The number of plumes increases from 16 at 700 K temperature jump to 21 at 1000 K and 26 at 1400 K. Furthermore, both variations from the reference temperature of 1000 K show distinctively lower fits between created plumes and observed hotspots. In the case of the CMB700 model,

Fig. 3.4 : Plumes and hotspots and their clustering properties are shown on top of the present-day topography. Plumes/Hotspots are marked with triangles coloured according to their cluster affiliation and the marked gray gray diamonds represent the position of the corresponding cluster centroids. Coastlines are plotted for reference. **(a)** Today's hotspot locations at Earth's surface (according to the catalogue described in Subsection 2.4.3). **(b)** Plumes in reference model CMB1000. **(c)** Plumes in a model without a bottom chemical boundary layer (TNC). **(d)** Plumes in the model CMB1000L, which is initiated out of an already convecting state.

Fig. 3.5 : Variations in the core-mantle boundary temperature change the large-scale convection pattern in a rather minor way. However the position of individual plumes is affected significantly (a-f). This also leads to significant changes in the probability distribution (g,h). Note that although the fraction of plumes close to hotspots is relatively similar between CMB700 and CMB1400 for high distances (right part of yellow and green line in bottom left panel) the different number of plumes in these models result in significantly different probabilities in the bottom right panel.

this is because plumes that particularly well resemble hotspots in the reference model - like the East-African plume, or the Mid-South Atlantic plumes, as well as the South Pacific plumes - do not exist. The plumes in the model CMB1400 are more numerous, but their position fits the observed hotspot position less accurate than the CMB1000 model, in particular the northern Pacific upwelling, which is displaced northward and the east African plume, which now reaches the surface more close to western central Africa.

Please note that the difference in CMB temperature does not influence the viscosity profile of the bottom boundary layer significantly, since the strong temperature-dependency of the viscosity formulation leads to a viscosity that is already limited by the global limit for viscosity of $5 \cdot 10^{19}$ Pas for the smallest temperature jump. The higher excess temperature of plumes in the models CMB1000 and CMB1400 thus only lead to thicker plume conduits with this minimal viscosity and therefore higher plume flux.

In general the reference model CMB1000 seem to resemble observations best, therefore suggesting that an average CMB temperature jump between 700 K and 1400 K is reasonable, with the results being not extremely sensitive to the exact number.

3.2.2. Viscosity Profile

As mentioned in Section 2.3.4, the viscosity formulation is a major controlling parameter of mantle convection models. Since it is also associated with major uncertainties, models with three different viscosity models as described in Subsection 2.3.4 were created and compared to assess their influence. The differences in the temperature and viscosity fields are presented in Figure 3.6. It is apparent that the models show dramatically different convection patterns despite otherwise unchanged model parameters. The viscosity formulation by Steinberger & Calderwood (2006) favors separated plumes at the boundaries of steep-edged piles. The temperature isosurface +250 K hotter than background mantle features nearly constant viscosities of around $5 \cdot 10^{21}$ Pas, except for the upper and lowermost mantle. In a depth map 100 km above the core-mantle boundary the steep-edged piles clearly stand out as regions of particularly low viscosities compared to a background mantle of very high viscosities. It is noteworthy, that this high background viscosity is also supported by highly-viscous subducting slabs in this model, which decreases the average temperature outside of the piles, compared to the other two models.

The mixed viscosity formulation model TV2 favours ridge-like upwellings on top of more rounded pile topographies, although also some single plumes develop in the Pacific. Close to the core-mantle boundary, the viscosity of the +250 K isosurface is higher and additionally strongly increasing with depth from 10^{21} Pas in the uppermost lower mantle to $5 \cdot 10^{22}$ Pas close to the CMB. The viscosities close to the core-mantle boundary are equally high as in the CMB1000 reference model, but due to the less strong temperature-dependency the piles are more viscous in this case. This might also be the reason for the less steep pile geometry.

In the model TV with the formulation of McNamara & Zhong (2005), the same round-shaped piles develop that are observed in model TV2; however, the ridge-shaped upwelling is much stronger separated into single plumes. Moreover, the +250 K isosurface shows near constant viscosities, which is more similar to the reference model CMB1000

Fig. 3.6 : Effects of different viscosity descriptions. Left column: Viscosity profile by Steinberger & Calderwood (2006). Right column: Viscosity profile used in Bower et al. (2013). Middle column: Radial dependence of Steinberger & Calderwood (2006) and temperature-dependence of Bower et al. (2013). (a-g) Isosurface of +250 K colored according to viscosity. (h-i) Map view with the same colorscale 100 km above the core-mantle boundary.

Fig. 3.7 : Effects of simplified material description. The material description of model TS is strongly simplified, but the main findings of Subsection 3.1.2 still hold true. The similarity between plume positions and observed hotspots is reduced slightly, but still significant. The plumes in the Pacific hemisphere seem slightly more affected by the changes than the ones in the African hemisphere.

than the model TV2. The viscosities in the cold regions above the core-mantle boundary are in general lower than in the two other models, resulting out of a lower radial viscosity as well as a less strong temperature-dependency. The pile viscosity is roughly similar though slightly lower than in the TV2 model.

Despite the significantly changed convection pattern, all models generate plumes close to observed hotspot positions and therefore show similar results in the probability analysis, although the TV2 model shows a somewhat less good fit. The results of this analysis are shown in Appendix Figure B.2.

In summary, the generation of single plumes instead of ridge-like upwellings seem to require a reasonably low absolute viscosity, while the generation of steep topography at the pile edges is supported by a strong viscosity contrast, for example caused by a strong temperature-dependency of the viscosity.

3.2.3. Material Description

The material parameters described in Subsection 2.3.3 offer the highest amount of realism and self-consistency. However, this approach includes a large number of degrees of freedom and possibilities for errors, therefore its influence on the presented model results is tested. In this subsection, the minimal necessary complexity of material description is searched, for which the presented fit between plume positions and hotspot locations still hold. The simplified material description consists of a constant background density, linearly decreasing thermal expansivity to the core-mantle boundary, constant thermal diffusivity, a constant compositional density anomaly of 2 % and a constant gravity profile. Figure 3.7 presents the model results with the above described material model. Although the shape of individual plumes varies, and some plumes change their position slightly, the overall fit remains on a statistically significant level. In general, the plumes in the Pacific hemisphere seem to be more prone to these changes. This is consistent with the observation made in Subsection 3.1.1 that the African pile and plume shapes are stronger constrained by subducting slabs, while the Pacific hemisphere is stronger governed by internal dynamics, which might differ substantially because of small buoyancy changes.

In summary, the changes of the viscosity structure (Subsection 3.2.2) have a much more significant influence on the observed plume positions and pile shapes than incorporating a more consistent material model. However, this is only true for this kind of models and observations, and different for regional models investigating the shape of individual plumes during their ascent. Especially for cases, in which the buoyancy of the plume is close to zero, the material properties are determining whether the plume reaches the base of the lithosphere or fails / ponds in the mid-mantle, as is presented in Dannberg & Sobolev (2015).

3.2.4. Initial Condition of Temperature

As mentioned in Subsection 2.3.1, the initial condition of a mantle convection model may play a significant role for an extended amount of time. In an unconstrained convection model (without prescribed velocities at the surface) the usual approach to select an initial condition is to let the model evolve for a prolonged time period until characteristic values have reached a statistical steady state. Such values may be the rms-velocity, Urey number (heatflux ratio), average temperature or averaged surface velocity. For the presented analysis it is not clear whether a statistical random convection state is the most favourable initial condition, since the difference of such a statistical state and the "real" temperature distribution of the Earth might be larger than the difference of an artificial "no perturbation" initial condition. Therefore, the computationally less expensive "no perturbation" state was assumed for all of the models, and the difference to a "random steady state" initial condition was tested for especially important models.

Figure 3.8 shows the present day situation in these two cases for the reference model CMB1000. The ongoing convection (CMB1000L) leads to a higher number of plumes and more small-scale features of convection, still the overall fit between plume positions and hotspot locations holds true and the plumes still tend to rise from the margins of the thermo-chemical piles. The significant range of the plume-hotspot match is reduced and shifted to higher distances, which shows that plume positions are slightly shifted by

Fig. 3.8 : Effects of statistical steady state initial condition for the reference thermochemical model. (a-d) The convection pattern and generated plumes change visibly, in particular the number of plumes is increased in the model with initially ongoing convection. (e): Because the average plume generation mechanism remains unchanged, the ongoing convection model also reaches significant fits between model plumes and surface hotspots, although only for higher plume-hotspot distances. Note, that since the ongoing convection model generates many more plumes, the error bars in the top right panel are overestimated (calculated for the reference model), therefore its probabilities in the bottom right panel are significant, although the distribution is within the uncertainty of the reference model. See Figure 3.3 for a probability plot of model CMB1000L with uncertainties calculated for its plume count.

Fig. 3.9 : Effects of statistical steady state initial condition for thermal models. In contrast to Figure 3.8 the convection pattern in a purely thermal model initialized from an ongoing convection is much more similar to a "non perturbed" start. This suggests a shorter initialization time for a purely thermal convection model. Nevertheless, the statistical fit is affected in the same way as for thermo-chemical models.

initial convection anomalies.

The model starting from an ongoing convection (CMB1000L) shows significant agreement of around 50 % of the plumes that are closer than 1250 km to their nearest hotspot. The general shape of the probability curve is similar to the reference model. However, for all but the largest distances this model gives a worse fit than the reference model. This suggests that an initial density state has an influence after 250 Ma of prescribed surface velocity in mantle convection. Since the initial density state of Earth's convection at 250 Ma is not known, our approach of using an undisturbed initial condition seems to perform better than a random convection state. The ongoing convection model leads in general to a more distributed generation of plumes (Figure 3.8 **a,b**), although the above mentioned reasons for the remaining distance between plumes and pile edges still hold. A large percentage of plumes (60 – 80 %) rise from the edges of the piles and are tilted (generally outward from the pile) so that they reach the surface laterally displaced to their generation zone. A small number of plumes rise from areas of the pile, where it is ridge shaped, therefore this is the ideal position for a plume to rise. At last a small number of plumes – usually less than 10 – 20 % – also rise from the top of a larger pile (especially the Pacific one). Interestingly, these plumes belong to the oldest of the plumes observed at the present-day state. They are already present in the initial condition, and survive the 250 Ma of model runtime, in contrast to most of the oldest plumes. However, they are formed on top of the small chemical "patches" that are present in the initial state of CMB1000L, and end up "by chance" on top of the created piles, because the pile is build around them, when the dense material is pushed together. The effect that plumes get generated at pile edges and then tend to shift towards the center of the pile as described in Steinberger & Torsvik (2012) is not very pronounced in these models. A more in-depth comparison of plume movement at the edge of a thermo-chemical pile at higher resolution might provide further insight into the acting forces.

In the purely thermal case shown in Figure 3.9, the visible difference in the convection pattern and plume distribution is smaller. The plume generation zones are nearly unchanged; nevertheless, the fit between plume positions and hotspot locations is reduced. The smaller effect on the purely thermal convection pattern supports a shorter initialization time for a purely thermal convection model. Because there is no dense material that provides "plume generation zones" the convection adjusts quickly to applied boundary conditions.

The agreement between the thermal model (light blue) and the observations reaches similar significance as for the reference model (dark blue), but at higher distances. Compared to the reference model CMB1000 and the ongoing convection model CMB1000L (Figure 3.8) the plume generation zones in the isochemical model TNC seem to be equally distributed in the Pacific but more concentrated in the Atlantic (Figure 3.9 **a,b**). This supports the plausible assumption that slabs have an even stronger influence on plume generation in isochemical convection, where no dense material is hindering their lateral movement at the core-mantle boundary. In the purely thermal model there are no distinct piles but rather a number of small plume generation zones that loosely resemble the shape of the thermo-chemical pile edges in the other models.

In contrast to Figure 3.8 the convection pattern in a purely thermal model initialized from an ongoing convection (Figure 3.9 **b,d**) is more similar to a "non perturbed" start (**a,c**). This suggests a shorter initialization time for a purely thermal convection model, because whatever thermal structure exists at the beginning of the model run, is overcome

Fig. 3.10 : Influence of compositional initial conditions on results. Although the dense material gets shaped in the same way for all compositional initial conditions, the created plumes differ significantly (a-d). e shows that initial conditions that vary more strongly from present-day state show better correlation with present-day hotspots.

until the present-day state. Nevertheless, the statistical fit of plume positions is affected in the same way as for thermo-chemical models.

3.2.5. Initial Condition of Composition

In Figure 3.10 and 3.11, models that were started with the different initial conditions described in Subsection 2.3.1 but otherwise identical model parameters are shown. Figure 3.11 (a-f) highlights the small influence of the initial condition on the final position and shape of the dense material at the core-mantle boundary. Although the chemical material starts in significantly different shape, the present-day compositional piles are nearly identical. On the other hand, Figure 3.10 shows that the influence of the initial compositional field on the final temperature field is considerable. Although most plumes are still generated at the edges of the piles, the plume position in detail varies a lot, which

is also illuminated by the fact that the fit between plume positions and hotspot locations is not significant for the model CIC2. The differences in the convection pattern may arise from the non-physical assumption of vertical side walls of the initial piles, strengthened by the imbalanced density at the model start, causing the piles to broaden until the first slabs arrive at the core-mantle boundary. However, the broadening is not strong enough to flatten the piles to a layer like in the reference model CMB1000 as shown in Figure 3.11, which also shows a model time, when the broadening is stopped by the first slabs arriving at the core-mantle boundary. Most likely the difference in plume generation zones is caused by the remaining circular hill in Figure 3.11 (c) and (d). It acts as an additional nucleation point for plumes, which therefore are not generated as consistently as in the reference model at the outer edges of the piles. Initial piles far from the present-day position produce more similar plume distribution, which might be caused by the fact that they are stronger reshaped by subducting slabs, therefore the vertical side walls are destroyed and the plumes are generated at the edges. A possible improvement could be the usage of a tomography model as initial condition for the distribution of the composition, to test its compliance of the plume generation with the present-day Earth. As shown in Figures B.14 and B.17, the assumption of using only 80 % basalt as composition for the dense piles does not change the results dramatically, although the test model CIC2-100 shows somewhat larger similarity between plume distribution and hotspot distribution. This is mostly caused by the stronger flattening of the piles in the initial phase, which is compatible with the above drawn conclusion that initial vertical side walls in arbitrary positions cause plume generation in these arbitrary places, and are therefore not comparable to present-day Earth.

Additionally to the above mentioned interpretations, the similarity of the compositional piles of CMB1000 and CIC2,3,4 contradict the interpretation of Bello et al. (2014) that the unknown initial condition prevents mantle convection models from predicting motion for a timespan longer than around 100 Ma forward in time, even in the presence of velocity boundary conditions. While the general hypothesis that unknown initial conditions limit the forward prediction time of mantle convection models is undoubtedly valid, transferring this conclusion to models with prescribed surface velocities – as is suggested in their work – seems not reasonable, considering the similarity of the thermo-chemical piles in this model set.

3.3. Model Properties and Validating Observations

3.3.1. Seismic Tomography

As mentioned in Subsection 2.4.4, the comparison between convection models and seismic tomography seems straightforward, but hinges on a number of assumptions and simplifications. While both can provide global or regional temperature/seismic velocity maps, the direct comparison is only reasonable for large-scale features with strong amplitudes. Nevertheless, for the purpose of this thesis the comparison can provide valuable insights that help to evaluate the convection model by estimating, which regions are in particularly good agreement between convection models and tomography, and which need further investigation.

In a comparison of the convection model temperature field (Figure 3.12 a,d), modelled chemical piles (Figure 3.12 b,e) and the seismic tomography model Savani velocity field

Fig. 3.11 : a-f: The final pile shape that evolved out of different initial pile shapes. g-l: The broadening of the chemical piles, when prescribed as initial condition. g,j show the pile shape at the begin of the velocity boundary condition. h,k present the not final state at 150 Ma, when slabs start to influence the bottom boundary layer significantly, and i,l show the reference model at this time for comparison.

Fig. 3.12 : Position and shape of thermo-chemical piles in the reference model CMB1000 at present time compared to the LLSVPs near the core-mantle boundary. **a,b**: An isosurface of material 250 K hotter than the surrounding mantle shows the dynamics of plume development. It is coloured according to the height above the CMB. **c,d** plot a chemical isosurface of the convection model. The piles evolved from a uniformly thick layer at model start. **e,f** show isosurfaces of -0.75% seismic s-wave velocities of the model Savani (Auer et al., 2014) in the African and Pacific hemisphere, respectively. The surfaces are cut above a depth of 600 km to remove upper mantle influences and mid ocean ridges for clarity. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference at the surface and the core-mantle boundary is indicated as gray sphere. Because Savani features anomalies with larger magnitude but smaller spatial extent than SMEAN in Figure 1.1, we plot the -0.75% contour for better comparability.

Fig. 3.13 : Comparison of model plume positions with hotspot locations and seismic tomography. **a** and **b** present horizontal slices at a depth of 600 km (**a**) and 2790 km (**b**) showing the calculated shear-wave velocity in this mantle convection model. The shear-wave velocity from the tomography model Savani (Auer et al., 2014) is shown in the same depths in **c** and **d** respectively. Today's hotspot locations are marked with triangles coloured according to their cluster affiliation in **c** and **d**. **a** and **b** triangles show model plume locations, again coloured according to their cluster affiliation. The marked gray diamonds represent the position of the corresponding cluster centroids (**a,b** for model plumes, **c,d** for observed hotspots). Coastlines are plotted for reference.

(Figure 3.12 **c,f**) a number of similarities are apparent. The previously described piles are at similar positions to the LLSVPs in seismic tomography, and even regional features, like the north-eastern boundary of the African LLSVP, which seems to be shaped by the Neo-Tethyan slabs under the eastern Mediterranean Sea and Arabian Peninsula, are shaped very similar to tomographic models (see also Figure 3.13 **b,d**). This shape is also a significant improvement over previous studies of McNamara & Zhong (2005); Bower et al. (2013).

At 600 km depth, small areas of distinctively lower seismic velocities underlie a number of hotspots in seismic tomography (Figure 3.13 **c**) and most subduction zones in the model are observed in the same places as in tomography. Near the core-mantle boundary the comparison shows obvious similarities between the hot regions in the convection model (Figure 3.13 **b**) and the two LLSVPs in seismic tomography (Figure 3.13 **d**). Although the positions and rough shape of the slow/hot regions fit reasonably well, a number of differences are apparent especially in the regions of their connections. For example, the convection model shows a pronounced ridge between the two LLSVPs beneath Central America that is not visible in the upper mantle tomography slice (Figure 3.13 **b,d**). Furthermore, the south-eastern extension of the African LLSVPs that is visible in the tomography is not observed in the convection model. Since both regions are surrounded by fast slab-material, these differences are hints to missing model resolution concerning the behaviour of subducted slabs.

An additional detail in all models is a hook-shaped northward extension of the African LLSVP (Figure 3.13 **b**). It extends from western Africa northwards to Iceland and then bends east- and south-eastwards, ending under western Russia. In the same region recent seismic observations have shown a considerably sized ultra-low velocity zone under the Russian city Perm, therefore dubbed the Perm anomaly (Lekic et al., 2012).

Although the region seems to be possibly disconnected from the African LLSVP in the tomography, the accumulation of dense material in nearly all of our models suggests that the position of this anomaly is a probable place for upwellings in the core-mantle boundary region, as well as for accumulation of chemically distinct dense material, therefore supporting the seismological evidence.

Despite this improvement in comparison to previous studies, the north-eastward deviation of the Pacific pile from the LLSVP position as observed in earlier models (Bower et al., 2013) remains unchanged. This might be a hint to past – yet unknown – intra-Pacific subduction zones (van der Meer et al., 2012) or the need to revise the subduction history offshore North America as suggested by Sigloch & Mihalynuk (2013).

3.3.2. South Atlantic Observations

Within the SAMPLE priority programme (South Atlantic Margin Processes and Links with Onshore Evolution) of the German Research Association (DFG), the South Atlantic is investigated in a multi-disciplinary network of universities and research centres. Its primary areas of research are: "[...] the mantle dynamics and magmatic processes, the lithospheric structure, deformation processes and rifted margin formation, the post-rift topographic evolution and links to climate and tectonics, and the sedimentary processes and fluid systems." (<http://www.sample-spp.de>). This thesis is part of SAMPLE sub-project STE 907/8-1 "The link between subduction under South America and plumes and LIPs in the South Atlantic". Therefore, in this section selected tomographic slices

between South America and Africa will be discussed and compared to convection model results.

The comparison between the converted seismic velocities of the reference convection model CMB1000 and the selected tomography models Savani (Auer et al., 2014) and P07 (Amaru, 2007) is shown in Figure 3.14 for three different slices through the South Atlantic (A,B,C). The color scales are chosen for the purpose of comparing lower mantle convection features.

The left column of Figure 3.14 (**a,d,g,j**) represents a great-circle path including the South-Sandwich islands and the WALPASS array (slice A in panels **m,n**), for which seismological modelling is performed and interpreted in Kästle (2014). The position of the African LLSVP is similar in the models, however, the convection model features an eastward shift of the LLSVP by around 10-15 degrees. The shape of the LLSVP in the convection model features two uprising sides below East Africa and the Mid-Atlantic. Regions of low velocity in the mantle beneath East Africa can be seen in both tomography models (**d,j**), but in the South Atlantic only the Savani model shows a connection between the LLSVP and a rising structure with a velocity anomaly of about -0.8 %, which is fading in the upper mantle (black circle in **d**). P07 does not show this feature in the lower mantle, but it exhibits lower velocities in the transition zone at exactly the lateral position, where the rising structure from the Savani model reaches the transition zone (black circle in **j**). The upwelling is present over the whole mantle depth in the convection model (**a,g**). Due to the small anomalies, it is unclear whether the anomalies of Savani and P07 image this upwelling that gives rise to the Tristan, and Gough hotspots in the convection model. However the good positional agreement suggests this connection. An ongoing local tomography as part of SAMPLE phase III might provide further insights into the upper mantle structure beneath the Tristan hotspot.

The cold anomalies in slice A prove to be very similar, when comparing the convection model with the tomography models. In particular the shear-velocities are compatible, for example the subduction position and slab angle in panels **a** and **d**. Noticeable differences only occur at the core-mantle boundary. The South-American slab in the convection model, seems to push the LLSVPs much further and with stronger force than what could be implied from the tomography models. This also explains the mentioned eastward shift in the LLSVP position. Interestingly, the shift is not observed in the arrival positions of the upwellings at the surface, because it is partly compensated by

Fig. 3.14 (*facing page*) : Seismic velocity deviations along the Drake passage - WALPASS array great circle path in the reference convection model CMB1000 and seismic tomography models Savani and P07. Great-circle paths are plotted in b). Slice A, left column: Great-circle path South Sandwich Islands - WALPASS array. Slice B, middle column: Great-circle path Chilean subduction zone - WALPASS array. Slice C, right column: Equatorial slice. Note that the scales for δV_S and δV_P in the different models are chosen according to the sensitivity of the models to highlight comparable features.

the tilting of the plumes. While the Mid-Atlantic plume is strongly tilted toward the west in the convection model, it is rather vertical in the tomography model Savani. The East African Plume on the other hand is relatively straight in the convection model, but slightly tilted to the East in the tomography models.

Slice B (middle column, panels **b-k**) shows a great-circle path from the Chile trench towards Central Africa, which cuts nearly orthogonally through the western and eastern boundary of the LLSVP. The position of the LLSVPs fits very well in this more northern slice compared to slice A. The East African Plume is displaced slightly to the west in the convection model, but position and shape of the subducted slabs fit very well between convection model and tomography.

In the right column (**c-l**, slice C), which shows an equatorial slice, several differences between convection and tomography model are apparent. The LLSVP extends too far westward in the convection model, and the eastward tilt of the east African plume is again not reproduced. Additionally the tomography models suggest stalled slabs in the transition zone (black circles in panels **f,i**, and Figure 14 in Fukao & Obayashi (2013)). The stagnation of slabs is not observed in the presented convection models, because the resolution is not sufficient to accurately image processes at phase transitions and in the transition zone. Therefore, the agreement between convection model and tomography will be worse in regions with stagnant or slowed down slabs in the transition zone. Nevertheless, an interesting agreement between convection model and tomography is observed at the core-mantle boundary in the eastern part of slice C. In all models the CMB is covered by a fast anomaly, most likely ancient subducted slabs from the Japan- or Kuril-trench. Additionally, the anomaly is much stronger observed in S-velocities (panels **c,f**) than in P-velocities (panels **i,l**). It would be necessary to check, whether the resolution of P07 in this region is sufficiently good to allow an interpretation, but it seems like the conversion via the *Perple_X* database can provide good explanations for the apparent differences between P- and S-velocity anomalies at the core-mantle boundary.

In conclusion, the match between South Atlantic observation and convection models is reasonable in all regions that are not strongly affected by mid-mantle processes like slowed-down / stagnant slabs, which are not resolved in the convection model. Further research in this direction will be done in the SAMPLE sub-projects SI 1538/1-1, which aims to create a finite-frequency tomography of the South Atlantic lower mantle with core-diffracted P-waves, and STE 907/8-2, which will use the in this thesis created convection models to compute synthetic wave fields and compare those to observations from the WALPASS array.

3.3.3. Pile Area

Another possible comparison between models and observations exist as the area fraction of the core-mantle boundary that is covered by low-velocity material. As mentioned earlier, previous work has shown the area fraction covered to be around 21 % of the total area in the SMean tomography model (Burke et al., 2008) 92 km above the core-mantle boundary. This fraction, however, is dependent on the choice of tomography model. The recently published shear-wave tomography model Savani for example (Auer et al., 2014), features a LLSVP area fraction of around 14 %, as is shown as gray dashed line in Figure 3.15. The definition of the LLSVP area in Torsvik et al. (2006); Burke et al.

Fig. 3.15 : The percentage of the CMB area, which has seismic velocities more than 1 % slower than PREM is plotted for several model setups. For reference the values observed in the SMean (gray solid line, Becker & Boschi (2002)), and the Savani tomography model (gray dashed line, Auer et al. (2014)) are plotted. (a) The covered area does not significantly differ with varying initial temperature conditions. The model TNC features thermal convection, with a fraction of 6 % that is produced by thermal plumes. (b) The covered area is decreasing with increasing core-mantle boundary temperature jump. This is expected since the thermal buoyancy increases the topography of the piles. (c) With decreasing percentage of basaltic material within the piles the covered area decreases. This is essentially identical to decreasing the chemical density contrast as well as the chemical seismic anomaly to 80 % / 50 % respectively. (d) The reduction of initial layer thickness to a mantle volume fraction of 1.8 %/1.0 % decreases the covered area significantly.

(2008) – as being material more than 1 % slower than the lateral average – was of course chosen by the properties (in particular the lateral velocity gradients) of the tomography model SMean. Overall, Savani features larger amplitudes of velocity deviation with less lateral extent, therefore with a different LLSVP boundary of material 0.5 % slower than the lateral average the covered area fraction of the Savani model increases to 26 %. The LLSVPs in this case show similar shapes to the SMean model. For comparability, all further analysis will be done with the former definition of -1 % Vs anomaly.

The amount of CMB area that is covered by low-velocity material is mostly controlled by two factors: The volume of available low-velocity material, and the topography of this material. The topography in thermo-chemical models is controlled by the ratio of chemical to thermal buoyancy contribution (the buoyancy number), while in the thermal models the topography is always spot- or plume-like, therefore only a small cross-section of the plume contributes to the covered CMB area in these cases. The available volume is a sum of dense pile material and thermally hot plume material, and in all of the so far presented models the pile volume is either constant at around 2.7 vol% or zero in iso-chemical models. A fact to keep in mind is the loss of pile volume due to entrainment over the model runtime. However, in most presented models the integrated entrainment of pile material is less than 5 % of their volume because of the short model runtimes. Therefore, most of the area difference in Figure 3.15 is generated by differences in pile topography. Only the CMB1000-50 model in Figure 3.15 (c) shows a nearly complete loss of the initial layer, with more than 50 % of the layer entering the upper mantle. For long time entrainment experiments like Mulyukova et al. (2015); Li & McNamara (2013), a higher resolution and more sophisticated material tracking would be required.

Interestingly, most investigated models either fall above or below the range of seismic models as is shown in Figure 3.15 (a). The reference model CMB1000 features a covered area fraction of 42 % – around twice as high as the SMean model. This fraction does not decrease significantly if the model is started from an ongoing convection, which shows that the prescribed temperature of the dense basal layer in CMB1000 is close to the value it would reach in a steady state case and the entrainment over the initial phase of 500 Ma is low. The purely thermal model TNC only covers 6 % of the CMB with material more than 1 % slower than PREM. As mentioned above, in this model only the plume cross-sections contribute to this coverage. The material is nearly equally distributed between African and Pacific pile (49 % / 51 %), which does not agree with observations from seismology, showing the African LLSVP to be larger Burke et al. (56 % to 44 % according to 2008). This disagreement is mostly caused by the North-Pacific region, which is inside the Low-velocity pile in the convection model, but not in tomography. Likely reasons for this are discussed in Subsection 3.3.1.

The following series of models tries to investigate whether a meaningful model setup can be found that matches the approximate area fraction suggested by seismic tomography. First, the core-mantle boundary temperature jump seems a reasonable parameter to vary for this purpose. As mentioned in Subsection 2.3.2, this value is unconstrained by around ± 50 % and it directly converts into a change of the buoyancy number via the available thermal density. Figure 3.15 (b) shows this variation to be influencing the covered area fraction in an expected way. The increase of the CMB temperature jump from 700, to 1000 to 1400 K decreases the area fraction from 45 % to 34 %. The increase from 1000 K to 1400 K seem to have an unproportionally larger effect than the reduction to 700 K, which is likely explained by the fact that the thermo-chemical

boundary layer becomes unstable at these temperature jumps. This is also the reason why models with even higher core-mantle boundary temperature jumps will not provide a possibility to reach values of tomography models; the chemical boundary would quickly be entrained in the overlaying mantle, except it would have a particularly strong influx of new material (e.g. from subducting slabs).

The reduction of the chemical anomaly within the layer is a different way of changing the buoyancy number, although with slightly different consequences for this analysis than the temperature change above. While the temperature increase reduces the buoyancy number by increasing the thermal contribution and at the same time strengthening the temperature effect on seismic velocities, the reduction in chemical anomaly reduces the compositional buoyancy and seismic contribution alike. The focus will be laid here on the buoyancy effect. As is shown in Figure 3.15 (c) the reduction in chemical buoyancy from around 2.3 % to 1.8 % reduces the covered area from 42 % to 34 %. A further decrease to 1.2 % however, leads to an instability of the layer and a reduction of the area fraction to 6 %, essentially the value of the purely thermal model TNC. It might be possible to find model configurations in between that match the seismic observations at this model time; however, it is questionable, whether these boundary layer would be stable in a longer model run without additional anomalous material entering the boundary layer. For such an investigation, models with much higher resolution than the ones presented here would be required, as for example discussed in Mulyukova et al. (2015); Li & McNamara (2013).

Another way of modifying the covered area fraction is to vary the initial layer thickness and therefore the volume of the available chemical anomaly. The reduction from 2.7 vol% of the mantle to 1.8 vol% and 1.0 vol% indeed reduces the covered area fraction nearly proportionally from 42 % to 33 % and 23 % respectively. In particular the latter model is a promising candidate and is further investigated in Figure 3.16. Although the reduction in layer thickness leads to smaller piles in Figure 3.16 (a) and (c), the position of the piles remains very similar to the tomography model. In fact, the volume and topography of the Pacific pile visually seems to fit better in this case than in the reference case, it evolves as a nearly ridge-like feature. The plume distribution is less similar to today's hotspot distribution compared to the reference model, but still very significant. The plume clustering and the seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary (Figure 3.16 f,g) also demonstrate a convincing fit, with some improvements to the reference model. For example, in contrast to the reference model there is now no connection between African and Pacific LLSVP below Middle America, which is in line with the seismic tomography. Additionally, the African LLSVP in this model shows an indentation in West Africa towards the center of the plume cluster, as is observed in the tomography model. However, these are features that are at the scale of the possible resolution of tomographic models, therefore further investigation is necessary, preferentially with local seismic observations of higher resolution.

A similar Figure for the model CMB1000-1.8% is presented in the appendix B.20, but since its results are comparable to the reference model it is not discussed here in detail.

In conclusion, for a purely basaltic layer, only the volume reduction to 1.0 % of mantle volume (or 60 km layer thickness) reaches pile areas and volumes similar to the SMean tomography model as analyzed in Burke et al. (2008). This model is also visually a good match to the Savani tomography model, and shows similar plume generation zones as observed on Earth. However, it would need to be investigated whether a thin chemical

Fig. 3.16 : Summary of results for model CMB1000-1%. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. (e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. 3.17 : Skewness of the shear-wave velocity distribution in tomography and models. Shown is a histogram of the area fraction of the core-mantle boundary versus the seismic shear-wave velocity deviation from PREM (Dziewonski & Anderson, 1981). The tomography model Savani (Auer et al., 2014) shows a skewness of the seismic velocity distribution, with a maximum at 0.3–0.6 %. Many other tomography models feature a bimodal distribution (Hernlund & Houser, 2008) with another peak between -1.5 % and -2 %. The reference model CMB1000 features a gaussian distribution around $+1.2$ % and a separated narrower peak at -2 %. The purely thermal model TNC exhibits a gaussian distribution similar to Savani, but lacks its extended tail at low velocities. Instead, it shows a very small peak at velocities of -3 %.

boundary layer with this properties could survive in Earth-like convection for longer times, and what amount of influx of new material would be needed. An interesting follow-up study could feature a combination of reduced basalt content of 80 % and a pile volume of 1.8 vol%. This would also match observations of Mulyukova et al. (2015) that piles generated from accumulated oceanic crust at the core-mantle boundary often consist of material with a basalt fraction of 60–80 %.

3.3.4. CMB Velocity Skewness

As mentioned in Subsection 1.3, the seismic shear-wave velocity distribution close to the core-mantle boundary is bimodal, with a broad Gaussian distribution at positive velocity anomalies and a second narrower peak at low velocities. In this section the created velocity distribution in the thermo-chemical and thermal reference models is compared to the observed pattern of seismic tomography.

As is shown in Figure 3.17, significantly different patterns evolve in the convection models compared to seismic tomography. A purely thermal convection model fits the

broad Gaussian shape of the seismic tomography relatively well and shows comparable anomaly magnitudes of $\pm 1\%$. Despite this similarity, it shows an average anomaly value around 0% instead of a more positive value in tomography, and only a very little low-velocity excursion at extremely low velocities (around -3% , most likely caused by the plumes). The thermo-chemical convection model features a very pronounced bimodal velocity distribution, with a Gaussian peak of cold slab material around $+1.5\%$ and a very sharp excursion at -1.75% ; caused by the thermo-chemical pile and plume material. Although the anomaly magnitude in the convection model seems too high compared to explain the observations of the tomography, this might easily be caused by damping of the tomography model as discussed in Subsection 2.4.4 or the short convection model runtime, which suppressed dilution and mixing of pile material. Overall, the thermo-chemical model provides a better way of explaining the observed bimodal distribution, although it should be investigated whether tomography parametrization and damping alone could explain the amplitude difference, or whether the seismic velocity anomalies in the convection model are overestimated.

3.3.5. Slab Sinking Rate

Slabs sink through the mantle with characteristic velocities that are determined by their density anomaly and the viscosity of the surrounding material. Additionally, the material and flow field below them control their descent. In our model runs, the average sinking rate of lower mantle slab material at the initiation of convection is within $1.5 - 2.2 \frac{cm}{yr}$ (Figure 3.18 a). This is slightly less, but comparable to convection models by Steinberger et al. (2012); Bower et al. (2013). After the first slabs have reached the core-mantle boundary at 150 Ma BP in these new models, they form a "slab graveyard" around the thermo-chemical piles that is significantly colder and more viscous than the average mantle. This region hinders the descent of new slabs and reduces the slab sinking rate close to the core-mantle boundary to values as low as $0.2 \frac{cm}{yr}$ (Figure 3.18 b). The reduction in speed occurs gradually over time and converges to a relatively constant average sinking velocity, as can be seen in Figure 3.18 c). Although Steinberger et al. (2012) also discover such a slowdown of slab material in old subduction regions (a reduction from 3.0 to $1.6 \frac{cm}{yr}$ in their models), the slowdown in these new models is far more pronounced – nearly stalling subduction in the lowermost 500 km of the lower mantle. A likely explanation for the general lower velocities and in particular the stronger sensitivity to previously subducted material is the temperature-dependent viscosity formulation in the new models. While the convection models of Steinberger et al. (2012) capture the effect of the reduced slab buoyancy compared to the cold surrounding material, they assume viscosities that do not change with respect to temperature. Considering the increased viscosity of subducting slabs compared to the adjacent mantle and the "strong" slab-graveyard region slows down slab descent far more effectively.

The type of the chosen temperature-dependent viscosity formulation on the other hand, does not influence this main finding of a significant slowdown. The in the reference model CMB1000 employed viscosity formulation by Steinberger & Calderwood (2006) (Figure 3.18 c, blue line) in general shows lower sinking rates than the viscosity formulation used in the model TV (as used in Bower et al. (2013), Figure 3.18 c, orange line), which in turn shows a more pronounced slowdown of sinking rates. Nevertheless, convection models with both formulations approach an average sinking rate within the

Fig. 3.18 : The average slab sinking speed is plotted versus depth at a model time of 150 Ma BP (a) and today (b). Slab material for this plot is defined as material colder than average mantle and below 660 km depth. Additionally slab material that is moving upward (e.g. dragged upwards by a nearby upwelling or plume) is not considered for this averaging. In general the slab sinking speed decreases over model runtime as a "slab-graveyard" forms at the core-mantle boundary (c). The gray area shows the observed sinking speed as published by van der Meer et al. (2009).

range of $12 \pm 3 \frac{mm}{yr}$ suggested by van der Meer et al. (2009) based on seismic tomography (gray area in Figure 3.18 c). It is important to note that this averaged model slab sinking rate was computed only of slabs in the range of 660 km to 1870 km depth, thus excluding the upper mantle with very high sinking rates and the lowermost mantle with nearly stalled slabs.

Although this average value fits the observation nicely, a remaining question is the difference to the observation of van der Meer et al. (2009) that slab sinking velocity seem to be near constant throughout the lower mantle. A possible reason for the difference might be the resolution of the convection models. In an under-resolved model the thickness of boundary layers / slabs is overestimated, which would result in an overestimated strength of the modelled slabs in the convection model. This would increase their resistance to deformation and in turn slow down the descent close to the core-mantle boundary, where slabs get deformed significantly. Another possible mechanism to increase slab sinking would be a weaker post-perovskite phase in the D" region as suggested by Ammann et al. (2010) and investigated in Nakagawa & Tackley (2011). If slabs weaken upon arrival at the CMB, this could increase deformation within the "slab-graveyard", and allow a nearly constant slab sinking rate of about $1.2 \frac{cm}{yr}$.

3.3.6. Temperature and Heat Flux Evolution

The thermal evolution of a mantle convection model is an indicator for its convection behaviour. For example a convection model that reached an steady state after a long model runtime will feature a more or less constant average temperature and a surface heatflux that is the sum of bottom heatflux and radiogenic heating. As mentioned in Subsection 2.3.1 the convection models presented in this thesis are either started from a prescribed temperature profile (with a thermal boundary layer that develops in 70 Ma) or an ongoing convection with no-slip boundary condition at the surface. The thermal properties of two models representing these initial conditions are presented in Figure 3.19.

As shown in panel **a** the mid-mantle temperatures in both models do not change significantly between model start and present-day state – a consequence of the relatively short model runtime of 250 Ma. The boundary layers, however, change significantly. In the reference model, the initial boundary layer is very close to the present-day state, which shows that the boundary layer age of 70 Ma is well chosen (also an average age of subducted oceanic plates). A much thicker boundary layer has developed in the initially convecting model, which is caused by the no-slip boundary condition and not ideal in terms of model evolution as discussed below. Since over time the thickness of this boundary layer is controlled by the prescribed plate velocities, the surface layers become more similar over time, and are essentially identical at the present state. The bottom boundary layers are more similar at the model start. However, the step-wise prescribed temperature profile is changed in the convecting model into a gradual temperature increase towards the CMB. Both bottom boundary layers show lower temperatures at the present-day state, but in quite different ways. The present-day bottom boundary layer in the CMB1000 model cools slightly and smoothes the step-wise temperature increase into a gradual one. This resembles the shape of the initial CMB1000L boundary layer. The present-state bottom boundary layer in the CMB1000L model, however, experiences a much stronger temperature decrease by around 200–250 K 100 km above the CMB. This decrease is likely caused by the subduction of the initially thick and cold top boundary

Fig. 3.19 : Temperature and heat flux evolution of the models CMB1000 and CMB1000L starting from the different initial conditions. **a** shows the difference of the laterally averaged temperature profile over depth between initial (at the start of the plate reconstruction) and final state. **b** shows the evolution of the globally averaged model temperature. **c** presents the RMS velocity and **d** the surface and core-mantle boundary heatflux.

layer, that now lies at the core-mantle boundary and heats up very slowly (at diffusion timescales of many hundred millions to billions of years). Therefore, it can be regarded as an artifact from the assumed boundary condition.

Panel **b** evaluates the evolution of the averaged model temperature over the plate reconstruction range of 250 Ma. As mentioned in Subsection 2.3.1, the model CMB1000L and TNCL start with a higher averaged temperature that developed in the first phase of no-slip convection. Here, the more interesting number to evaluate is the difference of averaged temperature (the secular cooling rate) over the model runtime. This number has been calculated for the Earth in different publications, for a detailed review the reader is referred to Jaupart & Labrosse (2006), but they state a possible range of 120 ± 70 K/Ga. Our models show varying values, but due to the above mentioned reasons model CMB1000 is assumed to show the more realistic temperature evolution and lies with ≈ 100 K/Ga (25 K per 250 Ma) well within the calculated range. The model CMB1000L features a value of 60 K/Ga.

Of course the temperature evolution is a direct consequence of the difference between bottom heatflux into the model plus the internal heat generation, compared to outward heatflux at the surface. Therefore, panel **c** states the evolution of the spatially integrated bottom and surface heatflow. The radiogenic heat generation in our model is assumed to be constant with time, which seems a valid assumption for the model time of 250 Ma (according to Jaupart & Labrosse (2006) the averaged half-life of heat producing elements on Earth is around 3 Ga). Note that the continental material in the model does not have an increased radiogenic activity, therefore the model is likely missing a contribution of 6-7 TW of heat generation (Jaupart & Labrosse, 2006). Keeping this in mind, the surface heatflux in the models of 30-40 TW (around 32 TW for present-day) is close to estimates for Earth's present-day surface heatflux of 41-47 TW (Stacey, 1992; Jaupart & Labrosse, 2006; Davies & Davies, 2010). Also very interesting is the contribution of the bottom heatflux, which increases from 4 to around 8 TW during the evolution of the reference model, while the model CMB1000L generally exceeds this number by 1 to 2 TW. These numbers are within the recently published range of core-mantle boundary heatflux of 5-13 TW (Lay et al., 2008).

Panel **d** shows the root-mean-square velocity of the models. This quantity is often used to determine the state of convection of a particular model. For comparison the model TNP is plotted, which features a free-slip surface boundary condition, and develops a stagnant lid convection with very low heat-flux through the surface. It is apparent that the beginning of the plate reconstruction (marked with a black line) increases the rms-velocity in the CMB1000L model significantly (blue line), and therefore influences the convection compared to the not influenced model TNP. It is questionable, however, whether a stagnant lid convection would be the appropriate comparison for this value. Ideally, a model with self-consistent plate tectonics at the surface would be required as discussed in Rolf et al. (2012). This model would produce higher rms-velocities, possibly comparable to the models CMB1000, CMB1000L. Unfortunately, the necessary rheological model and boundary for self-creating plate tectonics is not available, and presumably not stable in CitcomS. Therefore, without a proper comparison model the rms-velocity of the presented model is only of limited use, also because this property can not be constrained for Earth's mantle by observations.

In conclusion, although the models were not designed to fit Earth's thermal evolution and are certainly not in a steady-state of convection, they fit observations about the

Earth quite well. Two things should be kept in mind with this interpretation. First, the values for Earth's core-mantle boundary heatflux and mantle secular cooling rate are rather uncertain, therefore a wide range of models can reproduce them. Second, the Earth itself is not in an equilibrium convection state, but rather cooling over time. Therefore, the comparison of a model, which is not in thermal equilibrium, with the Earth does not seem completely unreasonable.

4. Testing Plate Reconstructions with Mantle Convection Modelling

4.1. Motivation

Due to the good agreement of the model results to present day observables – as discussed in Chapter 3 – it seems plausible to use this connection to constrain the controlling boundary conditions, in particular to test hypotheses for paleo-plate movements. The models constructed in this way are by no means unique, i.e. the variation of other model parameters might provide different solutions to the posed questions. However, since the results in Chapter 3 showed the major role of the boundary conditions in constraining the plume generation zones, it seems likely that an uncertainty in the boundary conditions will be one of the most essential parameters to test.

This work focusses on two questions concerning the modification of the used plate reconstruction by Seton et al. (2012):

- What influence does a rotation of the general reference frame as suggested by van der Meer et al. (2009) have on the longitudinal position and shape of plumes and thermo-chemical piles?
- Would a change in a regional subduction zone behaviour have a profound effect on the shape and position of present day plumes? More precisely, can the position and convergence parameters of a paleo-subduction zone be constrained by testing different scenarios and comparing the results of the global convection models to current-day observations?

4.2. Plate Reconstruction Scenarios

The plate reconstructions investigated in this work are variations of the Phoenix - South Gondwana subduction zone (today at the Pacific-Antarctica margin) around Triassic - Jurassic times (250 – 150 Ma BP). This area has been a part of the Australides (Vaughan & Livermore, 2005) or Gondwanides (Cawood, 2005) orogen and for a detailed review the reader is referred to Harley et al. (2013). The uncertainty in the plate reconstruction of this region arises from the unknown timing of accretion / generation of several outboard terranes and magmatic arcs like parts of the Antarctic Peninsula and several provinces of the Marie Byrd Land. These terranes "which preserve a history of episodic magmatism, coupled with multiple stages of contractional and extensional deformation" (Harley et al., 2013) have generally been formed between 400 Ma and 230 Ma, with the exact ending of movement being rather unclear. While the accretion and ocean-ward movement of the terranes seems to have ceased until 176 - 183 Ma BP, the deformation and magmatism of the created blocks have continued until the Palmer Land Event at 110 Ma (Vaughan

Fig. 4.1 : The unmodified subduction zone (1) was varied by position (panel **a**; Scenario 2,3), convergence velocity (panel **b**; Scenario 5,6) and convergence direction (panel **c**; Scenario 7,8). Scenario (4) is used for comparison to scenarios (5-8) and is essentially identical to case (2) except that it incorporates the reference frame rotation by van der Meer et al. (2009) discussed in Subsection 4.2.2. Models (1-3) use the original reference frame and models (4-8) incorporate the modification of the reference frame.

& Livermore, 2005). Thus, it is not clear if these terranes had already been accreted or were still isolated island arcs during the early stages of the Gondwana breakup (v.d.Meer pers. comm.).

The constructed models are investigated with the same observations discussed in Chapter 3, but the regional character of the changed plate reconstruction does not change the global distribution characteristics of plumes as can be seen in Figures B.22 to B.28. Therefore, only the regional consequences will be discussed here.

4.2.1. Subduction Zone Position

As stated in the introduction of this section, the exact position of the subduction zone along the western Antarctica boundary is only constrained up to an uncertainty of 2000 km. Therefore, plate reconstructions assuming one of three different positions for this subduction zone are constructed and employed in the convection models. The first one is the reference position by Seton et al. (2012), which includes all the mentioned terranes and therefore assumes that the accretion and subduction zone movement was already completed around 250 Ma (blue line, Scenario 1 in Figure 4.1 **a**).

The second one is referred to as the 'close' setup, in which the subduction zone separates mainland Antarctica (defined by the Ross orogen) from the accreted terranes (green line, Scenario 2 in Figure 4.1 **a**). This is an end-member case, since several of the mentioned terranes, like the Ross province in Marie Byrd Land and the Eastern Domain in the Antarctic peninsula show signs of Gondwana-derived sediments earlier than this time (Pankhurst et al., 1998; Mukasa & Dalziel, 2000; Siddoway & Fanning, 2009; Vaughan & Storey, 2000). But even though these terranes might have been accreted already, this scenario does also represent the effects of a possible regional flat-slab subduction scenario (v.d.Meer personal communication).

Additionally, a 'far' test case is constructed in which the subduction zone was moved

2000 km away from the coast into the Panthalassa ocean (brown line, Scenario 3 in Figure 4.1 **b**). This scenario is mostly considered a sensitivity test to check whether there is any influence of such a change in the plate reconstruction. Nevertheless, the existence of yet unknown intra-oceanic subduction zones in general is hard to constrain and the discovery of new zones can not be ruled out (van der Meer et al., 2012), therefore this scenario is more than a mere sensitivity test model. It would of course require a second subduction zone along the Antarctica margin to satisfy the geologic observations of convergence close to the continent margin.

The resulting pile shapes, plumes and seismic velocity fields are presented in Figure 4.2. Interestingly the 'close' subduction scenario does not cause a northward shift of the dense pile, but a broadening of the southern boundary (panel **b**). The change in subduction zone position creates a transform-fault between the shifted and non-shifted segments of the subduction zone and a disconnected slab at the modified subduction zone position. This part adjusts its descent angle to lie on top of the other slab, so that less internal deformation is necessary. This doubling of slabs can also be observed at some recent subduction zones as for example described and illustrated by Fukao & Obayashi (2013) for the Tonga-Kermadec trench, although there the slabs do stagnate at the mid-mantle, while here they rather sink to the core-mantle boundary. Since the slabs occupy less area at the core-mantle boundary when folded like this, the lateral extent of the dense pile is less affected by the subducted material.

The 'far' subduction scenario on the other hand causes a significant change in pile boundary position. The southernmost edge thins to a narrow wedge that is extending much further south than in the reference scenario (panel **c**). An additional feature of the 'far' subduction scenario is observed in Figure 4.2 **g** in the southern Pacific hemisphere. In most convection models, the Pacific pile extends significantly further south than observed in the Savani tomography model. However, in Scenario 3 the subduction zone is closer to this boundary and the subducting slab pushes it northwards – closer to the observed low-velocity regions. The sudden trench advancement after the reconstruction modification, which is essentially a jump of the trench towards the subducting plate, leads to the overturn of the subducted slab and to an initial push of the slab towards the Pacific region. This way the available force to push the African pile is significantly reduced, because less cold material is deposited next to it. Therefore, while Scenario 3 seems unlikely when only observing the South Atlantic and Africa, it provides more reasonable results in the Pacific hemisphere. A plate scenario with an additional intra-oceanic subduction zone that provides the force to push the Pacific pile into its observed position could therefore provide further insight. Nevertheless, it would require conformity tests with geological observations.

As demonstrated in Chapter 3, the plume positions are highly sensitive to the pile boundary shape and position – in particular the curvature of pile boundaries. Therefore, the different shape of the southern pile boundary creates new focus zones for upwellings.

The southward extension of the pile in the 'far' scenario strongly favours plumes far more South than in the reference model, with an uncommon 'shovel-like' upwelling structure (see Figure 4.2 **f**, bottom). Interestingly, although the pile shape resembles the northern extension of the African pile, the resulting thermal upwelling differs significantly. The upwelling in the North Atlantic forms a typical ridge-like structure, in which velocities converge in a line at the core-mantle boundary that merge into a plume-like or sheet-like upwelling (as for example shown in Figure 3.12). In the South Atlantic on

Fig. 4.2 : Subduction zone position influence on pile shape and plume generation. **a,b,c**: The compositional pile shape for Plate Scenarios 1,2,3, with the green arrows showing the approximate direction of slab push. Coastlines are plotted in black and plate boundaries in gray for spatial reference. **d,e,f**: The resulting convection temperature isosurface 200 K above average mantle temperature. Colour of the surface shows height above the CMB, green spheres show observed hotspot positions and gray lines denote surface plate boundaries. **g**: A slice of the tomography model Savani ~ 100 km above the CMB. Isocontours show the shape of low-velocity regions in the convection models 1,2,3 above.

Fig. 4.3 : The figure from van der Meer et al. (2009) shows the longitude correction applied to the reference frame. The correction is based on the identification of paleo-slab remnants in global p-wave tomography and fitted slab sinking velocities throughout the mantle. Shown are the possible fits between observed slabs in the tomography model and the longitude rotation of the reference frame that is necessary to achieve this fit for times back to 250 Ma BP. The observed depths of subducted slabs are converted to ages by an average sinking velocity for slabs.

the contrary, the upwelling seems to be shaped by a detachment of the bottom thermal boundary layer that then rises nearly as a horizontal sheet and only in the upper mantle separates into single plume-like upwellings. During the remaining 30 Ma of the model run (all models are run 30 Ma 'into the future' with current-day plate velocities), this shape is relatively stable.

The 'close' scenario on the other hand creates a more pronounced kink in the south-westward edge of the pile, because of the broadening of the pile boundary, which acts as a new focus zone for plume generation (see also the discussion about focus zones in Subsection 3.1.1). Therefore, the upwelling close to the Mid Atlantic Ridge develops as a pronounced plume instead of a relatively broad and diffuse upwelling in the reference scenario. This plume reaches the surface close to the present-day positions of the Discovery and Shona/Bouvet hotspots. Due to the good agreement with South Atlantic hotspots this scenario is considered more likely than the reference and the 'far' scenario.

4.2.2. Reference Frame Rotation

For plate reconstructions incorporated into geodynamical models the employed reference frame is of special importance as also discussed in Subsection 2.3.2. Although many geological observations only provide relative information about the position of two observed geological features, the comparison to global datasets of the present-day Earth makes it inevitable to create a global reference frame to which this relative information relates.

Fig. 4.4 : The present-day model state of the "close" model (Setup 2, panels **a,c**) is nearly identical to the "both" model with applied reference frame rotation (Setup 4, panels **b** and **d**). For all further models (4-8) the reference frame rotation will be applied.

Common approaches to construct reference frames include the position of hotspots or magnetic poles (O'Neill et al., 2005; Steinberger & Torsvik, 2008), while more recent work has incorporated seismic, geodynamic and other observations to constrain in particular the paleo-longitude (van der Meer et al., 2009; Doubrovine et al., 2012; Conrad et al., 2013; Domeier & Torsvik, 2014). In this work the influence of the longitude correction suggested by van der Meer et al. (2009) is tested, which is based on the remnants of subducted slabs visible in seismic tomography. In summary, the concept involves the generation of a fit function between the reconstructed subduction zone positions and the observed slab remnants of a certain depth in dependence of the longitude rotation of the global reference frame. The conversion between slab depth and subduction zone age is constrained separately, but with the same tomographic dataset. Following this routine, they calculate a westward longitude correction of up to 18 degree at 150 Ma BP as plotted in Figure 4.3.

The influence of the reference frame rotation on the final pile boundary and plume shape is plotted in Figure 4.4. The pile position is moved westward by a few degrees and the shape of the southern boundary is extending further south in the eastern edge instead of the western edge. Additionally, the buoyancy flux of the three created plumes is shifted more towards the westernmost plume, which now also features a splitting of the plume stem into two separate channels close to the surface, in a comparable distance to

the Shona/Bouvet hotspots. This feature shows the possibility of complex plume shapes to develop in the interplay between plate movements and plume ascent, but also the relatively minor change introduced by the reference frame correction by van der Meer et al. (2009).

4.2.3. Convergence Velocity

As long as there is no present day observed hotspot track or ocean floor remnants with magnetic anomalies, in particular oceanic plate velocity reconstructions are completely dependent on extrapolations into the past or continental observations that might provide hints to their movements. Therefore, the relative velocity between the Phoenix plate and Antarctica prior to 160 Ma is quite unconstrained. In order to investigate the effect of a different convergence velocity, three velocity scenarios are created. All scenarios use the rotated reference frame discussed in Subsection 4.2.2 and the subduction zone position scenario 4 from Subsection 4.2.1. The Scenario 4 (green arrows in Figure 4.1 **b**), which is used for comparison, uses the original Phoenix plate velocities from Seton et al. (2012). The "fast" Scenario 6 doubles the already fast rotation velocity of the Phoenix plate around its absolute Euler pole of around $10 \frac{cm}{yr}$ - increasing its speed to around $20 \frac{cm}{yr}$. Since the movement of Gondwana during this time is relatively slow, the change is nearly equivalent to doubling the convergence velocity at the subduction zone. The "slow" Scenario 5 (yellow arrows in Figure 4.1) reduces the rotation velocity to half the reference value ($5 \frac{cm}{yr}$), effectively halving the convergence velocity.

Although the velocity variations applied are quite significant, they only cause minor variations in the pile boundary shape. The increased velocity leads to a larger amount of subducted material and accordingly to a northward shift of the pile boundary (Figure 4.5 **c,f**). A slower convergence velocity generates slightly less pushing force for the pile boundary and allows a southward extension of the pile (Figure 4.5 **b,e**). The influence on the plume positions of all three setups is minor, suggesting that the whole-mantle flow field is not very much affected by the speed of an individual subducted slab. However, it is remarkable that while plume positions in general are very sensitive to pile boundaries, in these cases the change in pile boundary is counteracted by changes in the plume shape in a way that leaves the plume arrival positions nearly unchanged. A possible explanation for this behaviour is given by the fact that the western and eastern kink of the pile boundary is less affected than the middle part of the southern boundary, and thus the plume generation zones are relatively similar. Therefore Scenarios 4, 5 and 6 are considered equally likely, and it seems difficult to constrain the subduction velocity of a particular slab by this method.

4.2.4. Convergence Direction

For the purpose of changing the convergence direction of the subduction zone, the absolute Euler pole of the subducted Phoenix plate was calculated with GPlates and replaced by a point that was rotated $30^\circ / 60^\circ$ along a small circle around the approximate central position of the subduction zone. This leaves the average velocity of the Phoenix plate unchanged, although the orthogonal convergence velocity at the subduction zone was reduced by changing the convergence direction from a relatively straight subduction to a more oblique setting. All scenarios feature the same reference frame as described above

Fig. 4.5 : Influence of convergence velocity changes on the pile shape and plume distribution in the South Atlantic. **a,b,c**: The compositional pile shape for Plate Scenarios 4,5,6, with the green arrows showing the approximate direction of slab push. Coastlines are plotted in black and plate boundaries in gray for spatial reference. **d,e,f**: The resulting convection temperature isosurface 200 K above average mantle temperature. Colour of the surface shows height above the CMB, green spheres show observed hotspot positions and gray lines denote surface plate boundaries. **g**: A slice of the tomography model Savani close ~ 100 km above the CMB. Isocontours show the shape of low-velocity regions in the convection models 4,5,6 above.

Fig. 4.6 : Influence of convergence direction rotation on pile shape and plume distribution in the South Atlantic. **a,b,c**: The compositional pile shape for Plate Scenarios 4,7,8, with the green arrows showing the approximate direction of slab push. Coastlines are plotted in black and plate boundaries in gray for spatial reference. **d,e,f**: The resulting convection temperature isosurface 200 K above average mantle temperature. Colour of the surface shows height above the CMB, green spheres show observed hotspot positions and gray lines denote surface plate boundaries. **g**: A slice of the tomography model Savani close ~ 100 km above the CMB. Isocontours show the shape of low-velocity regions in the convection models 4,7,8 above.

and are plotted in Figure 4.1 **c** (Scenario 7, 30 degrees rotation, dark green arrows, Scenario 8, 60 degrees rotation).

The final position and shape of the pile is plotted in Figure 4.6. Changing the convergence direction leads to a more westward arrival of the slab forming the boundary of the pile. This allows the pile to extend further south-eastward and some material in the beginning of the model run is pushed over to the Pacific pile. The south-eastward extension is also observed in the Savani tomography model (Auer et al., 2014) and many other s-wave tomography models (e.g. Ritsema et al., 2011; Panning et al., 2010), and is best resembled by a rotation of the Phoenix plate subduction velocity by 30 degrees.

The 60 degree rotation scenario allows the pile to extend even further southward, with a much narrower southern ending. Additionally, the African pile loses a significant amount of material, which is integrated in the Pacific pile. A comparison of the ratio between African and Pacific pile volume reveals that the rotation of the subducting slab moves material towards the Pacific pile, which now contains 57 % of the total pile volume, compared to 52 % in the 30 degree rotation model and 48 % in the comparison model "both".

The influence on temperature field and plume positions is equally pronounced as discussed in Subsection 4.2.1. Figure 4.6 shows a clear correlation between longitude extent of the pile and number of plumes generated ranging from three plumes in Scenario 4 to one focussed upwelling in Scenario 8.

Given the widespread distribution of hotspots in the South Atlantic and south of Africa on Earth, Scenario 4 shows the most similar plume distribution compared to observations.

4.3. Excluding Setups

The constraints on specific plate reconstructions by convection models are often non-unique and this is also true for this particular model set. But although a precise determination of a best-fitting model is relatively difficult, a number of model setups can be excluded due to their incompatibility with seismic tomography or hotspot positions. As shown in Figure 4.7, the plate reconstruction Scenarios 3 and 8 ('far', '60 degrees rotation') are determined to be very unlikely. However, although Scenario 3 ('far') does not fit the African hemisphere, it provides good agreement with seismic tomography for the southern boundary of the Pacific pile with seismic tomography. A scenario with two subduction zones, one intra-oceanic and one at the continent boundary, might be an option for further investigations. Scenarios 2, 4 and 7 ('close', 'both', '30 degrees rotation') on the other hand can be considered as possible improvements to the existing plate reconstruction and their agreement with geologic and seismologic data should be tested in more detail. The discussed observables do not show a particular sensitivity to Scenarios 5 and 6 ('slow', 'fast'), therefore the determination of the most likely convergence speed of the Phoenix-Gondwana subduction is not possible from these model results.

However, it has been shown that convection models can serve as a valuable tool for constraining some parameters of the plate motion history of the Earth in particular regions.

Fig. 4.7 : The investigated models can be divided in likely, possible and unlikely reconstruction scenarios (marked by green, yellow and red colors). Gray models do not show a particular sensitivity to the changes, therefore the investigated features can not be constrained by this set of models.

5. Conclusion

In the course of this work a number of hypotheses concerning the interaction between subducted slabs and plume generation zones have been tested and evaluated. In particular, the position of the generated plumes, the clustering of their distribution, the influence of model parameters, the comparison to seismic tomography models, and general model properties like thermal evolution, heat flux, and slab sinking speed were discussed. This chapter summarizes the findings in a conclusive way:

- The hotspot positions on today's surface are determined by the past plate motion history and can be reproduced with statistical significance in mantle convection models.
- Plumes favour the margins of thermo-chemical piles to rise. In particular, kinks or bends of these margins act as focus zones of plume generation. The concept of "plume generation zones" at the margins of thermo-chemical piles can therefore be specified to sharply bend regions.
- The differences between a thermo-chemical core-mantle boundary layer and a purely thermal one are – although significant in the seismic properties of the inner regions of the LLSVPs – not significant in terms of the resulting plume distribution to exclude one of the two hypotheses. The final plume positions of a purely thermal convection model are equally close to the present-day hotspot distribution as the ones from a model with dense piles at the CMB.
- The recently suggested "Perm" anomaly (Lekic et al., 2012) is reproduced for a wide parameter range in the presented convection models, which supports the seismological observation on a regional scale. This is a significant advancement over previous model studies, which only show comparability to seismic tomography on the largest scales.
- While the incorporation of composition-dependent material properties has a massive influence on the dynamics of single plumes (Dannberg & Sobolev, 2015), its influence on the global distribution of plumes is only small. This indicates that the final hotspot position is not crucially influenced by the plume buoyancy and ascent time, but mainly by the plate motion and related mantle flow field.
- A much larger influence on the plume distribution is exerted by the employed viscosity formulation, whereby strongly temperature-dependent viscosity formulations like Steinberger & Calderwood (2006) usually provide more earth-like plume distributions.
- The initial conditions of a chemical boundary layer or the initial convection state in a plate-guided mantle convection model is usually overcome after 150-200 Ma.

Minor convection features like individual plume positions are different, but the general regions of upwellings are very similar.

- A parameter study of the properties of the compositional boundary layer suggests a volume fraction of less than 2 % of the mantle and a basalt content of 60–80 % to reproduce the observed area fraction of the core-mantle boundary that is covered by the dense material.
- Convection models can be used to validate and improve employed plate reconstructions used as model input, by comparing the model results to other observations. This can be exploited to test seismological predictions like the ones made for the North-Pacific in van der Meer et al. (2012); Sigloch & Mihalynuk (2013) or for the eastern boundary of the African LLSVP in Kästle (2014).
- The comparison of plate configurations in the Southern Panthalassa ocean and the Southern Gondwana subduction zone shows that the subduction of the Phoenix plate was likely closer to Gondwana or in a flat-slab scenario, and potentially oblique. The results proved relatively insensitive to the convergence velocity.

6. Outlook

This study presents new insights into the interaction of subducted slabs and plume generation zones. In this complex topic, there still remain open questions and motivation for further studies:

As has been discussed in Subsection 3.3.1, the comparison between convection and tomography models has shown a good fit for low-velocity regions. The high-velocity zones do not agree as well, which shows that the slab behaviour is potentially insufficiently resolved, especially in places with stagnant slabs in the transition zone. A higher resolution – in particular at phase transitions – and a more sophisticated slab rheology might improve this behaviour and lead to more realistic slab behaviour also at the CMB.

Several regional observations are currently planned or recently finished in the area of the South Atlantic (e.g. O'Connor et al., 2012; Rohde et al., 2013; Kästle, 2014). They provide excellent constraints on the type of convection model presented in this thesis, and should be used to further evaluate smaller-scale features, as will be done in the SAMPLE project STE 907/8-2. This can especially improve our knowledge about the timing and coupling between rifting processes and mantle plumes.

New plate reconstructions have been published recently (Domeier & Torsvik, 2014), and were used to investigate the stability of thermo-chemical piles (Bull et al., 2014). They provide better constraints on the surface motion, in particular in earlier times, than the ones investigated in this thesis. With a boundary condition further back in time, the influence of the initial condition on the model solution could be decreased even further. Additionally, the longer plate reconstructions might allow the comparison of past plume head arrival times and plume motion in the convection model with eruptions of large igneous provinces and the movement of hotspots in moving hotspot reference frames on Earth.

This thesis neglects geoid and dynamic topography observations as comparison criteria. This is partly related to the decision to include continents with relatively arbitrary density anomalies to reduce the amount of subducted basaltic material to a reasonable amount. However, they cause significant density variations, dominating the topography field. Therefore, for a comparison to dynamic topography a more sophisticated approach must be used, for example excluding lithospheric density anomalies from the calculation of dynamic topography. Alternatively, a model without continents could be investigated, in which the amount of subducted oceanic crust must be carefully controlled, for example by adjusting the thickness of the oceanic crust and lithosphere, or the control of subduction angle and slab temperature and velocity field like in Bower et al. (2013, 2014). Nevertheless, the comparison to geoid and dynamic topography observations on Earth could provide another validation for the presented models.

The comparison to seismic data done in this thesis can be improved by the application of tomographic resolution operators to the convection model as is done by Bull et al. (2009); Schuberth (2009). Alternatively, the convection model seismic velocity field can be used to model direct seismic observations like in Nissen-Meyer et al. (2014) and

compared to observations like Kästle (2014), which is planned for SAMPLE subproject STE 907/8-2. This would make the amplitudes of seismic anomalies more comparable between the models, and could evaluate which features on Earth can be resolved by different seismic methods.

The previously published theories and observations for Intra-Panthalassan subduction zones (van der Meer et al., 2012; Sigloch & Mihalynuk, 2013) can be investigated by incorporating their plate setups into the convection models and compare the present-day states of models. Although early plate reconstructions included an North-Pacific intra-oceanic subduction zone (e.g. the one used in Steinberger, 2000b) it was discarded in newer works about global plate reconstructions. Considering the above mentioned regional observations, it would be a possible future extension of this study to introduce such subduction zones and investigate whether they could solve the discrepancy between guided convection models and tomography, which was observed both in Bower et al. (2013) and this study.

Selbstständigkeitserklärung

Hiermit versichere ich, dass ich die vorliegende Dissertation ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter und ohne Benutzung anderer als der angegebenen Literatur angefertigt habe. Die Stellen der Arbeit, die anderen Werken wörtlich oder inhaltlich entnommen sind, wurden durch entsprechende Angaben der Quellen kenntlich gemacht. Diese Arbeit hat in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form noch keiner Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegen.

Potsdam, 25. November 2014

René Gaßmüller

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List of Figures

1.1. SMEAN tomography model with hotspots, large igneous provinces and kimberlite eruption positions	13
1.2. Trace element distribution in MORB and OIB	15
1.3. Nd vs. Sr isotopes in MORB and OIB	16
1.4. Limitation of plume generation zones by subducting slabs and thermo-chemical piles	19
2.1. CitcomS mesh organization	25
2.2. Influence of the solver tolerance	26
2.3. Runtime of different solver tolerances	26
2.4. Initial condition for temperature	29
2.5. Initial Composition Distribution	31
2.6. Comparison of the used material descriptions	35
2.7. Comparison of the used viscosity descriptions	38
2.8. Created model setups	43
2.9. Statistical comparison of point data sets	45
2.10. Determination of suitable cluster algorithm parameters	47
2.11. Used hotspot catalogue and spatial clustering.	49
3.1. Time evolution of reference model	54
3.2. Probability distribution for plume-generation zones	56
3.3. Probability distribution for additional models	57
3.4. Clustering of model plumes	59
3.5. Effects of core-mantle boundary temperature	60
3.6. Effects of simplified viscosity description.	62
3.7. Effects of simplified material description	63
3.8. Statistical steady state initial condition in chemical models	65
3.9. Statistical steady state initial condition in thermal models	66
3.10. Influence of compositional initial conditions on results.	68
3.11. Initial broadening of piles and final pile shape	70
3.12. Position and shape of thermo-chemical piles compared to seismic tomography	71
3.13. Comparison to seismic tomography maps.	72
3.14. South Atlantic - Walpass array great circle slices.	74
3.15. CMB area covered by piles	77
3.16. Summary of results for model CMB1000-1%	80
3.17. Skewness of seismic velocities at CMB	81
3.18. Slab sinking speed over time	83
3.19. Evolution of temperature and heatflux	85

4.1. Reconstruction plate setups.	90
4.2. Subduction position influence	92
4.3. Longitude corrected reference frame	93
4.4. Reference frame rotation influence	94
4.5. Convergence velocity influence	96
4.6. Subduction direction influence	97
4.7. Summary of investigated reconstruction setups.	99
B.1.	128
B.1. Complete time evolution of reference model - African hemisphere	129
B.1. Complete time evolution of reference model - Pacific hemisphere	131
B.2. Probability statistics for viscosity comparison	132
B.3. Statistical comparison of point data sets - distance	132
B.4. Summary of results for model CMB1000	134
B.5. Summary of results for model CMB700	135
B.6. Summary of results for model CMB1400	136
B.7. Summary of results for model TNP	137
B.8. Summary of results for model TNC	138
B.9. Summary of results for model TS	139
B.10. Summary of results for model TV	140
B.11. Summary of results for model TV2	141
B.12. Summary of results for model CMB1000L	142
B.13. Summary of results for model TNCL	143
B.14. Summary of results for model CIC2	144
B.15. Summary of results for model CIC3	145
B.16. Summary of results for model CIC4	146
B.17. Summary of results for model CIC2-100	147
B.18. Summary of results for model CMB1000-50	148
B.19. Summary of results for model CMB1000-80	149
B.20. Summary of results for model CMB1000-1.8%	150
B.21. Summary of results for model CMB1000-1%	151
B.22. Summary of results for model "Close"	152
B.23. Summary of results for model "Far"	153
B.24. Summary of results for model "Both"	154
B.25. Summary of results for model "Slow"	155
B.26. Summary of results for model "Fast"	156
B.27. Summary of results for model "30degrees"	157
B.28. Summary of results for model "60degrees"	158

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A. Data

A.1. Hotspot Catalogue

Table A.1. : Used hotspot catalogue data.

Name	Lat [°N]	Long [°E]	Age [Ma]	Index	Pacific hemisphere	South Atlantic	Secure
Yellowstone	44.6	-110.5	15	1	1	0	0
Raton	37	-104	20	2	1	0	0
Bowie	53	-135	28	3	1	0	0
Balleny	-66.8	163.3	36	4	1	0	0
Cobb	46	-130	43	5	1	0	0
Guadelupe	27	-113	25	6	1	0	0
Jan Mayen	71.1	-8.2	210	7	0	0	0
Socorro Island	18.7	-111	25	8	1	0	0
Iceland	65	-19	60	9	0	0	1
East Australia	-38	143	50	10	1	0	0
Tahiti	-17.9	-148.1	5	11	1	0	1
Tasmanid	-39	156	50	12	1	0	0
Juan Fernandez	-34	-82	30	14	1	0	0
Fernando	-4	-32	70	15	0	1	0
Eifel	50	7	40	16	0	0	0
San Felix	-26	-80	30	17	1	0	0
Louisville	-51	-138	120	18	1	0	1
Caroline	5	164	80	19	1	0	0
Trindade	-20.5	-28.8	120	20	0	1	0
Lord Howe	-33	159	50	21	1	0	0
Kerguelen	-49	69	117	22	0	1	0
Galapagos	-0.4	-91.5	85	23	1	0	1
St Helena	-18	-10	100	24	0	1	0
Azores	38.5	-28.4	100	25	0	1	1
Marquesas	-11	-138	9	26	1	0	0
Comores	-11.8	43.3	63	27	0	1	0
Canary	28	-18	65	28	0	1	1
Macdonald	-29	-140.2	120	29	1	0	0
Marion Island	-46.9	37.8	195	30	0	1	0
New England	29	-32	120	31	0	1	0
Hoggar	23	6	20	32	0	1	0
Pitcairn	-25	-129	8	33	1	0	0
Samoa	-15	-168	14	35	1	0	1
Tristan	-38	-11	125	36	0	1	1
East Africa	6	34	40	37	0	1	1
Cameroon	4.2	9.2	31	38	0	1	0
Reunion	-21.2	55.7	67	39	0	1	1
Tibesti	21	17	80	40	0	1	0
Hawaii	19.4	-155.3	100	41	1	0	1
Darfur	13	24	140	42	0	1	0
Cape Verde	15	-24	20	43	0	1	0
Easter Islands	-27.1	-109.3	68	44	1	0	1
Hainan	20	110	?	45	1	0	1
Shona	-51.6	1	?	46	0	1	0
126 Discovery	-45	-4.7	?	47	0	1	0

B. Models

B.1. Additional Figures

Fig. B.1

Fig. B.1 : Shown is the time evolution of the African hemisphere of the reference model. The isosurface represents temperatures 250 K hotter than average mantle. The colours represent height above the core-mantle boundary and coastlines are plotted for spatial orientation. Green spheres are plotted at current-day hotspot positions and blue spheres represent current-day plume positions in the model.

Fig. B.1 : Shown is the time evolution of the Pacific hemisphere of the reference model. The isosurface represents temperatures 250 K hotter than average mantle. The colours represent height above the core-mantle boundary and coastlines are plotted for spatial orientation. Green spheres are plotted at current-day hotspot positions and blue spheres represent current-day plume positions in the model.

Fig. B.2 : Probability statistics for viscosity comparison. The different viscosity formulations produce largely different convection patterns, but the fit to the observed hotspot positions stays equally valid.

Fig. B.3 : This figure plots identical data as Figure 2.9 but plotted against the distance between hotspot and model plume instead of the integrated area fraction that is covered by circles of this distance around every hotspot on Earth's surface. The difference between the two plots is therefore the (nonlinear) scaling of the x-axis.

B.2. Model Summaries

Fig. B.4 : Summary of results for model CMB1000. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.5 : Summary of results for model CMB700. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.6 : Summary of results for model CMB1400. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.7 : Summary of results for model TNP. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.8 : Summary of results for model TNC. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.9 : Summary of results for model TS. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.10 : Summary of results for model TV. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d) Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.11 : Summary of results for model TV2. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.12 : Summary of results for model CMB1000L. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.13 : Summary of results for model TNCL. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.14 : Summary of results for model CIC2. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.15 : Summary of results for model CIC3. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.16 : Summary of results for model CIC4. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.17 : Summary of results for model CIC2-100. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.18 : Summary of results for model CMB1000-50. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.19 : Summary of results for model CMB1000-80. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.20 : Summary of results for model CMB1000-1.8%. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.21 : Summary of results for model CMB1000-1%. Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.22 : Summary of results for model "Close". Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.23 : Summary of results for model "Far". Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.24 : Summary of results for model "Both". Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.25 : Summary of results for model "Slow". Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.26 : Summary of results for model "Fast". Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.27 : Summary of results for model "30degrees". Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Fig. B.28 : Summary of results for model "60degrees". Shown is the visual comparison of model compositional piles (a,c) and LLSVPs in the tomography model Savani (b,d Auer et al., 2014) for the African (a,b) and Pacific (c,d) hemisphere. e) presents the model plume distribution compared to the observed hotspots and the significance of this comparison. Further a map view of seismic velocities close to the core-mantle boundary is presented for the convection model (f) and tomography model (g). Triangles denote model plumes (f) and hotspots (g) coloured by their cluster affiliation respectively, and diamonds show the centroids of the resulting clusters. Coastlines are plotted for spatial reference.

Curriculum Vitae

Excluded from published version.

List of Publications

van Hinsbergen, D.J.J., Steinberger, B., Doubrovine, P.V. & Gassmüller, R. (2011): “Acceleration and deceleration of India-Asia convergence since the Cretaceous: Roles of mantle plumes and continental collision”. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 116(B6):B06101. doi: 10.1029/2010JB008051.

Zeumann, S., Sharma, R., Gassmüller, R., Jahr, T. & Jentzsch, G. (2014): “New Finite-Element Modelling of Subduction Processes in the Andes Using Realistic Geometries”. In: C. Rizos & P. Willis (Eds.), *Earth on the Edge: Science for a Sustainable Planet SE - 13*, International Association of Geodesy Symposia, vol. 139, 105–111. Springer Berlin Heidelberg. ISBN 978-3-642-37221-6. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-37222-3_13.

